

Appendix to “Modeling the Impact of Space Weather on Planetary Space Environments”

Souvik Roy

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Appendix A

Historical overview of early observations of aurora and the geomagnetic field

During the post-medieval period or specifically, the early modern era, evidence of auroral sightings started showing up more frequently in literature. Fig. A.1 shows various drawings of auroras during 1770-1879 from different corners of the world. Tycho Brahe, the famous astronomer, documented auroral occurrences between 1582 and 1598 from his Uraniborg observatory in Denmark. With that, starting from the beginning of the seventeenth century, scientific theories regarding the origin of the northern lights began to emerge¹ In around 1610, Galileo Galilei observed sunspots for the first time. During that time, he also proposed that the aurora was caused by air rising out of Earth's shadow, becoming illuminated by sunlight. Ironically, both sunspots and the aurora are considered modern-day easily observable space weather phenomena. Between 1619 and 1623, Galileo (or possibly the French mathematician and astronomer Pierre Gassendi) coined the term "aurora borealis," meaning "dawn of the north," which comes from "Aurora," the Roman goddess of dawn, and "Boreas," the Greek god of the cold wind, storms, and winter, personifying the northern wind.² Evidence exists that both Pierre Gassendi from the southern region of France and Galileo in Venice witnessed an identical auroral event on September 12, 1621. It was Gassendi who first deduced that auroral displays must occur at great heights, given their consistent configuration observed at distant locations. René Descartes, his contemporary, on the other hand, suggested that auroras were caused by reflections from ice crystals in the air at high latitudes.

¹For a brief historical overview of auroras and space weather, refer to the first chapters of Moldwin (2022); Russell et al. (2016) and references therein.

²On February 17, 1773, Captain James Cook became the first European to witness the southern lights in the Southern Hemispheric Indian Ocean, which he referred to as aurora australis.

Figure A.1 **(A)** A depiction of red auroras over Japan in mid-September 1770 (Courtesy of Hayakawa et al. (2017) and the National Diet Library). **(B)** Aurora Borealis captured on October 24, 1879, at Guildford, London; taken from “Aurorae: Their Characters and Spectra” by John Rand Capron (Fuller, 2014). **(C)** Aurora Borealis observed on March 1, 1872, at 9:25 PM local time by French artist, illustrator, astronomer, and biologist Etienne Leopold Trouvelot (Plate IV from *The Trouvelot Astronomical Drawings* 1881). **(D)** Artwork from “L’aurore boréale” by Selim Lemström, 1886.

Between approximately 1645 and 1715, both solar activity and auroral sightings declined. Edmund Halley (the name behind Halley’s Comet), after observing an auroral display after this low activity period, at the age of 60, was among the first to suggest a connection between the aurora and Earth’s magnetic field. In 1731, French philosopher Jean-Jacques d’Ortour de Mairan dismissed the prevailing notion that the aurora was a reflection of polar ice, proposing a connection to the solar atmosphere instead. Even early measurements of auroral height were made by him in 1726, later refined by English scientist Henry Cavendish in 1790, estimating it to be between 80 and 112 km. Then much later, Norwegian scientist Carl Størmer accurately determined auroral height around 1900 using the advent of photographic techniques. Like Edmund Halley, De Mairan also suspected a link between the

return of sunspots and the aurora. Subsequently, studies of geomagnetism and the aurora became more closely intertwined.

Figure A.2 Angles of force on the “terrella”: An illustration portraying the magnetic dipole nature of Earth’s primary magnetic field, as depicted in Gilbert’s work, “De Magnete.”

Besides auroras and sunspots, the geomagnetic field is one of the three natural phenomena systematically observed, marking the inception of the exploration of space weather. Similar to auroras, early indications of the geomagnetic field trace back to the prehistoric era. In 1088, Chinese encyclopedist Shen Kua (or Shon-Kau) described compasses, noting how *“fortune-tellers rub the point of a needle with the stone of the magnetic in order to make it properly indicate the south.”* By the sixteenth century, figures like Georg Hartmann and Robert Norman contributed to a better understanding of the geomagnetic field. In 1600, William Gilbert, later Queen Elizabeth’s personal physician, published “De Magnete,” a renowned six-book treatise exploring Earth’s magnetic properties and illustrating its constant orientation in the universe. Figure A.2 depicts Gilbert’s woodcut, illustrating the distribution of magnetic inclination or dip across the Earth and a small spherical lodestone referred to by him as a “terrella.” Despite Gilbert’s belief in a constant terrestrial magnetic field, subsequent individual works by Henry Gellibrand, Edmund Halley, and George Graham (between 1635 and 1722) revealed the most basic nature of the Earth’s magnetic field that we still agree with – it’s a magnetic dipole with regular and irregular variations due to different factors.

Appendix B

A historical overview of extreme space weather events

B.1 Most intense geomagnetic storm in recorded history: the Carrington event

In the early hours of Thursday, September 1, 1859, Richard Christopher Carrington¹, a British astronomer, was observing a significant grouping of sunspots through a projected image of the Sun at his private observatory in Redhill (Surrey). Around 11:18 hours Greenwich mean time, as noted in his report, his attention was captivated by an intensely luminous white patch above the prominent dark spots. This bright patch gradually diminished to a pin-point and disappeared within about sixty seconds of emerging (see Figure B.1). In his report to the Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society (Carrington, 1859), Carrington described the scene as:

“ ...when within the area of the great north group (the size of which had previously excited general remark), two patches of intensely bright and white light broke out, in the positions indicated in the appended diagram by the letters A and B, and of the forms of the spaces left white. My first impression was that by some chance a ray of light had penetrated a hole in the screen attached to the object-glass, by which the general image is thrown into shade, for the brilliancy was fully equal to that of direct sun-light; but, by at once interrupting the current observation, and causing the image to move by turning the R.A. handle, I saw I was an unprepared witness of a very different affair. I thereupon noted down the time by the chronometer, and seeing the outburst to be very rapidly on the

¹For amusing anecdotes about Mr. Carrington and his work, read the book by Clark (2019)

Figure B.1 Richard Carrington produced illustrations on September 1, highlighting the sunspot that triggered the most powerful white-light flares (panel A) and the complete solar disk (panel B). Panel B depicts the Sun's rotational axis as an inclined line, with the sunspot responsible for the Carrington flare situated in the upper-left quadrant of the solar disk. Additionally, sunspot sketches by Heinrich Schwabe on September 1 (panel C) and a detailed close-up depiction from the same date (panel D). Image courtesy: Royal Astronomical Society and Hayakawa et al. (2019a)

increase, and being somewhat flurried by the surprise, I hastily ran to call some one to witness the exhibition with me, and on returning within 60 seconds, was mortified find that it was already much changed and enfeebled. Very shortly afterwards the last trace was gone, and although I maintained a strict watch for nearly an hour, no recurrence took place."

Simultaneously, Richard Hodgson, an English publisher and amateur astronomer, independently observed and reported the same event in the same journal by the Royal Astronomical Society (Hodgson, 1859). Like Mr. Carrington, he was also awestruck by this remarkable event and described it as:

BOMBAY MAGNETICAL OBSERVATIONS.											
DAILY OBSERVATIONS, FROM 1st to 4th SEPTEMBER 1859.											
DATE.	Latitude	Longitude	Barometrical Pressure	Thermometer at Height	Vertical Force Magnetometer	Horizontal Force Magnetometer	Abnormal Horizontal Force	Abnormal Vertical Force	Computed Dip.	Direction.	DATE.
Month	Time	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	1850.	Month
Sept. 1st	12	22 24	14.78	81.3	63.23	81.78	820.20	2501.5	105.99	N	4 12 p.m.
13	24 09	15.23	81.2	63.27	81.7	820.0	2501.1	105.92	N	5 12 "	
14	25 14	15.56	81.1	63.34	81.4	820.4	2502.2	105.79	N	6 12 "	
15	26 18	16.02	81.2	63.55	81.5	820.2	2502.2	105.58	N	7 12 "	
16	26 59	16.49	81.7	63.59	81.9	820.2	2503.2	105.37	N	8 12 "	
17	27 21	17.07	82.4	63.58	82.9	820.1	2504.1	105.17	N	9 12 "	
18	28 02	18.11	83.3	63.98	82.7	820.0	2505.0	104.94	N	10 12 "	
19	30 00	18.44	84.2	63.85	82.5	820.0	2505.0	104.73	N	11 12 "	
20	30 19	18.45	84.2	63.85	82.5	820.0	2505.0	104.73	N	Noon.	
21	22 27	14.54	85.2	63.99	84.5	820.2	2506.2	104.52	N	1 12 p.m.	
22	15 45	14.00	85.3	63.93	85.0	820.4	2507.4	104.33	N	2 12 "	
23	17 28	14.00	85.4	63.41	85.3	820.3	2508.3	104.14	N	3 12 "	

BOMBAY MAGNETICAL OBSERVATIONS.											
DISTURBANCE OBSERVATIONS, 1859.											
Date and	Disturbance.			Horizontal Force Magnetometer.			Vertical Force Magnetometer.			Direction.	Time.
	Latitude	Longitude	Time.	At Foot	At 4 m.	At 8 m.	At Foot	At 4 m.	At 8 m.		
Sept. 1st.	18.15	20.70	20.20	15.27	28.22	83.6	81.0	63.0	82.0	N	4 12 p.m.
13	24.09	15.23	81.2	63.27	81.7	820.0	2501.1	105.92	N	5 12 "	
14	25.14	15.56	81.1	63.34	81.4	820.4	2502.2	105.79	N	6 12 "	
15	26.18	16.02	81.2	63.55	81.5	820.2	2502.2	105.58	N	7 12 "	
16	26.59	16.49	81.7	63.59	81.9	820.2	2503.2	105.37	N	8 12 "	
17	27.21	17.07	82.4	63.58	82.9	820.1	2504.1	105.17	N	9 12 "	
18	28.02	18.11	83.3	63.98	82.7	820.0	2505.0	104.94	N	10 12 "	
19	30.00	18.44	84.2	63.85	82.5	820.0	2505.0	104.73	N	11 12 "	
20	30.19	18.45	84.2	63.85	82.5	820.0	2505.0	104.73	N	Noon.	
21	22.27	14.54	85.2	63.99	84.5	820.2	2506.2	104.52	N	1 12 p.m.	
22	15.45	14.00	85.3	63.93	85.0	820.4	2507.4	104.33	N	2 12 "	
23	17.28	14.00	85.4	63.41	85.3	820.3	2508.3	104.14	N	3 12 "	

Figure B.2 (Top) Passages extracted from the Colaba yearbook, presenting tables with hourly values for September 1–4, 1859, and spot-value tables for September 1–2, 1859. Image Courtesy: British Library Board and Hayakawa et al. (2022). (Bottom) Bombay (Colaba) Magnetogram of the horizontal geomagnetic field intensity covering the magnetic storm of September 2, 1859. Image Courtesy: Siscoe et al. (2006), originally modified from Tsurutani et al. (2003).

Figure B.3 Magnetograms at the Greenwich Observatory (British Geological Survey) started recording the Carrington Event on Thursday, September 1st, 1859, at 11:18 local time (23:18 recorded time). They measured 110 nT in horizontal magnetic force (H) and 0.283 degrees in Declination (D) of the compass direction. D, shown as the lower line on each image, precedes the upper trace of H by approximately 12 hours. The data collection spanned from August 29 to September 3 in each panel. Image courtesy: British Geological Survey.

*“...I was suddenly surprised at the appearance of a very brilliant star of light, **much brighter than the sun’s surface, most dazzling to the protected eye**, illuminating the upper edges of the adjacent spots and streaks, not unlike in effect the edging of the clouds at sunset; the rays extended in all directions; and the centre might be compared to the dazzling brilliancy of the bright star α Lyræ when seen in a large telescope with low power.”*

Approximately 17 hours and 40 minutes later, around 4 am the following day, the catastrophic event witnessed by humanity, characterized by Carrington as “a great magnetic storm” in his report, now serves as a benchmark for extreme space weather occurrences.

Following the documented white-light solar flare, there ensued an abrupt ionospheric disturbance, specifically, a significant magnetic crochet of approximately 110 nT. This occurrence implies a flare intensity of approximately X45, ranking it among the most substantial in the annals of observational history. As a result, the “Carrington event” stands out as an exemplary event and considered as one of the worst-case scenarios in terms of solar flare magnitude, solar wind speed, magnetic storm intensity, and the equatorward extension of auroral visibility (Refer to Baker et al., 2004; Boteler, 2006; Cliver and Dietrich, 2013; Cliver et al., 2000; Cliver and Svalgaard, 2004; Daglis, 2001; Dyer et al., 2018; Hapgood et al., 2021; Hapgood, 2011; Hayakawa et al., 2016, 2020; Hudson, 2021; Kimball, 1960; Lakhina and Tsurutani, 2016; National Research Council et al., 2008; Nevanlinna, 2008; Riley, 2012; Riley et al., 2018; Riley and Love, 2017; Tsurutani et al., 2003, and references therein).

Tsurutani et al. (2003) indicates that the change in magnetic response (ΔH) was 1600 ± 10 nT at the Colaba Observatory ($18^{\circ}56'N, 72^{\circ}50'E$), built in 1826 by the British East India Company for astronomical observations and timekeeping². Its purpose was to provide support to British and other shipping using the port of Bombay (or present-day Mumbai, India). They also argued that this substantial H-depression potentially leads to a Disturbance Storm Time (Dst; a quantifier for geomagnetic storms; discussed elaborately in the following sections) index of -1760 nT and the equatorial boundary of auroral visibility around -23° magnetic latitude (MLAT³). Nevertheless, recent studies have raised doubts about its preeminence in terms of magnetic storm intensity, particularly because it is unprecedented for the latitude of the station, posing challenges in interpretation if the negative excursion is considered equivalent to Dst. Figures B.2 and B.3 depict the magnetogram data during the event from Bombay (Colaba) and Greenwich Observatory, respectively.

Following Li et al. (2006) suggestion, Siscoe et al. (2006) replaced the original Bombay (Colaba) magnetogram data with hourly averages, creating a time profile closer to a typical Dst profile. The maximum H-depression is recorded as 850 nT (see Figure B.2). Hayakawa et al. (2020) also analyzed datable auroral reports from South America and its vicinity, identifying the auroral visibility at -17.3° MLAT or $-25.1^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ in invariant latitude (ILAT⁴). In a recent study, Hayakawa et al. (2022) demonstrated that the magnetic disturbance vari-

²The commencement of observations at the observatory took place in 1841 under the supervision of Arthur Bedford Orlebar, who held the position of Professor of Astronomy at Elphinstone College in Bombay (Mumbai) at that time.

³Magnetic latitude (MLAT), also known as geomagnetic latitude, is a parameter akin to geographic latitude. However, unlike geographic latitude, which is determined relative to the geographic poles, geomagnetic latitude is defined in relation to the axis of the geomagnetic dipole. This axis can be precisely derived from the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF; VanZandt et al., 1972).

⁴Invariant latitude (ILAT) denotes a parameter related to the magnetic field line, along which electrons traverse and induce the illumination of auroras (Hayakawa et al., 2018).

ation for the Carrington storm at Bombay is approximately -949 ± 31 nT. Even though the value dilutes than that of Tsurutani et al. (2003), it still stands as one of the top three known geomagnetic storms that humanity has ever faced. The other two are the 1872 February storm and the 1921 May storm.

B.2 Auroras in Indian sky: the Chapman-Silverman storm of February 1872

Approximately 12 years after the Carrington event, on a pleasant Sunday evening of February 4, 1872, the port city of Bombay (present-day Mumbai, India) experienced an extraordinary celestial event – one that seemed improbable given its magnetic latitude (MLAT) of around 10.0° . An aurora, displaying constant color changes and reaching a deep violet hue at its peak intensity, graced the sky. In sheer amazement, the Times of India, in its February 6 Bombay-based edition (See Figure B.4), reported the event with the opening line, ‘*Will it surprise our readers to learn that the Aurora Borealis was plainly visible in Bombay on Sunday night last?*’

Not only in Bombay but also in several other low magnetic latitude cities ($< |20|^\circ$ MLAT) like Darjeeling (West Bengal, India), Allahabad (Uttar Pradesh, India), Lucknow (Uttar Pradesh, India), Jaipur (Rajasthan, India), Rajkot (Gujarat, India), Bhavnagar (Gujarat, India), Lahore (Pakistan), Jacobabad (Sindh, Pakistan), Rawalpindi (Pakistan), Multan (Pakistan), Sukkur (Sindh, Pakistan), Bandar-e-Jask (Iran), Aden (Yemen), Mecca (Saudi Arabia), Khartoum (Sudan), Shanghai (China), Shaoxing (China) and from a major part of the European and Middle Eastern Countries, auroras were visible either at the zenith or at very high elevations (Hayakawa et al., 2023; RAO, 1964; Silverman, 2008). Magnetic variations during the event were also recorded at various locations across the globe along with the Bombay (Colaba) observatory: the Royal Observatory Greenwich ($51^\circ 29'N$, $00^\circ 00'E$, 50.6° MLAT), Tiflis ($41^\circ 43'N$, $44^\circ 47'E$, 36.7° MLAT), Hanover VT ($43^\circ 42'N$, $72^\circ 17'W$, 55.1° MLAT), St. Paratunka ($52^\circ 97'N$, $158^\circ 25'E$, 46° MLAT), and Havana Observatory ($23^\circ 08'N$, $82^\circ 21'W$, 34.1° MLAT).

At Colaba, a substantial negative excursion beginning around 18:00 UT resulted in a gap from 18:17 to 18:30 UT. During this interval, a deflector magnet was introduced to keep the H-trace on scale. Following this gap, the H-trace exhibited a positive excursion of approximately 300 nT within about 20 minutes (Figure B.5). The horizontal component, ΔH , of the Bombay magnetogram in Basu (1954, page 50), displays annotated amplitudes of the Sudden Commencement (SC) to be 85 nT, measured at 17:18 Bombay Local Mean

Figure B.4 (**Left column**) The report on the aurora, dated February 14, 1872, was featured on page 3 of the Englishman’s Overland Mail, a newspaper published in Calcutta (modern-day Kolkata, India) from 1864 to 1876. This publication was specifically intended for transmission to England and documented the occurrence of auroras in various cities, including Lucknow, Allahabad, Lahore, and Darjeeling. Image courtesy: The British newspaper archive. (**Right column**) The newspaper article describing the auroral phenomenon in Bombay, sourced from the second page of the Times of India’s February 6, 1872 Bombay-based edition, as referenced in Hayakawa et al. (2023). The original image is credited to the British Library Board.

Time (LMT) or 15:04 UT from the relatively stable pre-SC trace. It also indicates an H trace amplitude of 1023 nT. Since the strength of the deflector magnet is neither mentioned nor estimable, this amplitude measurement is taken from the peak of the SC to the first reading at 18:30 UT, just after the data gap, assuming no further negative excursion during this gap period.

Chapman (1957) categorized this event in the category of “outstanding auroras”, drawing a comparison to the Carrington storm by considering the observed auroras in Bombay. However, Silverman (1995) argued that the observed aurora in Bombay could have been erroneously associated with documented telegraph outages. Nevertheless, upon reassessment later, Silverman (2008) endorsed the authenticity of the sighting in Bombay, categorizing it as a sporadic occurrence of aurora. Based on his reconstruction of the equatorward boundary of auroral visibility during the event, Silverman (2008) contended that this occurrence surpassed the intensity of the Carrington storm (Kimball, 1960; Silverman, 2006; Tsurutani et al., 2003), taking it a step beyond Chapman (1957). The community now refers to the

A magnetic storm of great intensity was recorded by Colaba on this day. It was one of the most violent storms since 1857 listed by Chapman and Bartels (*Geomagnetism* Vol. I page 328).

Very intense Aurora Borealis was seen in many places and even in low latitudes like Bombay from the evening of 4th to the morning of 5th. The Aurora Borealis of this date is one of the most brilliant on record. Internal telegraphic Communication and cable communication with England were interrupted for some hours as a result of the storm.

(Bombay LMT is 4 hours 51 minutes ahead of G M T)

Figure B.5 Magnetogram data from the Bombay (Colaba) observatory on February 4 and 5, 1872, illustrates the horizontal magnetic force (HF) plotted on the top axes and the declination of the compass direction (D) on the bottom, depicted against the Local Mean Time (LMT) of Bombay which is 4 hours 51 minutes ahead of the Greenwich mean time or UT. A significant negative excursion, commencing around 18:00 UT, led to a gap from around 18:17 to 18:30 UT. In this interval, a deflector magnet was introduced to maintain the H-trace on scale. It also signifies an amplitude of 1023 nT for the H trace and 85 nT for the Sudden Commencement (SC). The unit nT is denoted as γ in the plot. The image is taken from Basu (1954, page 50).

storm as the Chapman–Silverman storm⁵, undoubtedly an extreme geomagnetic event with an estimated Dst of ≤ 834 nT (Hayakawa et al., 2023).

⁵For a detailed overview, read the recent study by Hayakawa et al. (2023).

B.3 The New York Railroad storm: latest in the extreme trio

The latest one, among the three largest magnetic storms yet observed and estimated, even based on just a single observatory, happened more than 100 years ago. The events unfolded back on May 12, 1921, when a massive sunspot, AR1842, made its appearance during the waning phase of Solar Cycle 15. This marked the beginning of a series of eruptions, with coronal mass ejections (CMEs) being propelled directly towards Earth. Over the ensuing three days, these CMEs rattled Earth’s magnetic field. Scientists worldwide were taken aback when their magnetometers suddenly registered off-scale readings, rendering their strip chart recorders useless as the pens maxed out at the paper’s top. Over-the-horizon radio communication was disrupted, causing interference such as static and fluctuating reception signal strength. Fuses blew on telegraph systems, and stray voltages on some wires exceeded 1,000 V, leading to fires erupting in various locations.

Figure B.6 Newspaper articles from New York, Pennsylvania, and Paris detailing the disruptions caused by the sunspots and aurora borealis to electric, telegraph wires, and railway systems.

The first signs of disruption to telegraph systems occurred at 14:30 Pacific local time on May 13, corresponding to a significant phase of disturbance as recorded by various instruments. The effects of the storm were particularly acute in New York City and across

Figure B.7 The figure depicts locations where auroras were observed on May 14-15, 1921. It includes both geographic and corrected geomagnetic latitudes, along with the day-night terminator for 05:30 UT on May 15, coinciding with the storm's peak. Image courtesy: Silverman and Cliver (2001). Observations corresponding to this event have been recorded and published by at least twenty-one different geomagnetic observatories: Agincourt (Canada), Alibag (India), Apia (Samoa), Cheltenham (USA), Christchurch (New Zealand), Eskdalemuir (UK), Greenwich (UK), Honolulu (USA), Kakioka (Japan), Kew (UK), Lyon (France), Meanook (Canada), Potsdam (Seddin) (Germany), Rude Skov (Birkerød) (Denmark), Sitka (USA), Stonyhurst (UK), Tortosa (Spain), Tsingtau (Qingdao) (China), Tucson (USA), Vasouras (Brazil), and Watheroo (Australia) (refer to Hapgood (2019) for more details).

New York State. By the afternoon of May 14, excessive electric currents on telephone lines caused the Union Railroad Station in Albany to catch fire and burn to the ground. Even during the evening of May 14, Mr. Hatch, a telegraph operator at the Central New England Railroad station in Brewster, was forced away from his keys by a sudden surge of "electric fluid," igniting the switchboard and setting the station ablaze. Meanwhile, the auroras over New York City were so luminous that even the intense lights of the electric signs along Broadway paled in comparison. By about 01:00 local time on May 15, numerous telephone lines connecting Brooklyn to Long Island ceased functioning due to blown heat coils and

arrestors. At 07:04 local time, the New York Central Railroad experienced a sudden halt below 125th Street when its signal and switching system failed, followed by a fire in the control tower at 57th Street and Park Avenue. The blame for the fire that destroyed the Central New England Railroad station was officially attributed to the aurora (see Figure B.6). The severity of the storm, reflected in the estimated Dst value of -907 ± 132 nT (Love et al., 2019a), contributed to the event being colloquially referred to as the ‘New York Railroad Superstorm,’ marked by the unfortunate fire and destruction of the New York rail properties⁶. Nonetheless, the storm not only affected the United States of America (USA), but it also interfered with telephone, telegraph, and cable traffic across Europe and Oceania, with reports of a burned-out telephone station in Sweden. Aurora sightings were reported in the Eastern United States and as far as Pasadena, California, with impact reports from various countries including Australia, Brazil, Denmark, France, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, and the United Kingdom (Figure B.7).

B.4 The list is long: spanning time immemorial

The lack of in-situ data for pre-space age storms poses a significant challenge in reconstructing these events through computer simulations to gain a better understanding of space weather devastation (Li et al., 2006; Manchester et al., 2006; Ngwira et al., 2014). To fulfill our aspiration of studying a well-documented and credible “worst case” scenario in space weather, the Sun presented an almost perfect opportunity on July 23, 2012. Around 02:08 UT on that date, it emitted a set of exceptionally powerful and extreme CMEs, observable from various space-based observation platforms stationed around Earth, including encounters with the STEREO-A spacecraft. Unfortunately (or rather, very fortunately), it took a path in the heliosphere away from Earth. But remaining within our line of sight, it served as a demonstration of how a “perfect storm” could materialize through a convergence of various factors and indicated that the occurrence of such a “perfect storm” scenario may not be as rare as conventionally assumed. The magnetic field strengths associated with this event would have triggered a significant geomagnetic storm had it impacted Earth. Extensive discussions on this event have been conducted by Baker et al. (2013); Liu et al. (2014); Ngwira et al. (2013); Riley and Love (2017); Russell et al. (2013); Zhu et al. (2016), focusing on elucidating its properties within the broader context of understanding extreme events and contemplating the potential ramifications had it impacted Earth. For instance, Liu et al. (2014) provided analytical estimates suggesting that the July 2012 storm could have driven

⁶For detailed review of the New York Railroad event, read the studies by Hapgood (2019); Love et al. (2019a); Silverman and Cliver (2001).

the Dst index to values between -598 nT and -1154 nT which was more impactful than the March 1989 storm if not comparable to the Carrington event. To clarify, the March 1989 storm is widely regarded as the most intense storm of the space age by conventional standards, with a minimum Dst of -589 nT (Kyoto), and -565 nT (Oulu). It is renowned for its impact on technological systems worldwide, including satellite operations, over-the-horizon radio communication, navigational systems, and geophysical surveys (Bolduc, 2002; Love et al., 2022; Stanislawska et al., 2018, and references therein). Thus, it's not hard to imagine what the consequences to society would have been if the July 23, 2012 CME had hit the Earth.

On one hand, the July 2012 event marked a significant leap forward in terms of data accessibility compared to the 1859 event. On the other side, a recently uncovered yet equally intriguing study represents a commensurately large step backward. Fusa Miyake, a cosmic ray physicist at Nagoya University, Japan, conducted doctoral research on measuring isotope abundances, leading to the identification of plausible geomagnetic storm events in the wood of long-lived Japanese cedar trees, now termed the Miyake events. A Miyake event manifests as a sharp enhancement in the production of cosmogenic isotopes by cosmic rays, evidenced by a spike in the concentration of radioactive carbon isotope ^{14}C in tree rings, with the year of occurrence determined through dendrochronology (Jull et al., 2014; Miyake et al., 2014, 2013, 2012, 2019; Zhang et al., 2022), as well as ^{10}Be and ^{36}Cl in ice cores (Usoskin et al., 2013), independently dated. Currently, five significant events are known (7176 BCE, 5259 BCE, 660 BCE, 774 CE, 993 CE) with remarkable spikes in ^{14}C exceeding 1% rise over a 2-year period, and four additional events (12350 BCE, 5410 BCE, 1052 CE, 1279 CE) require independent confirmation. The frequency of Miyake events remains unknown, but based on available data, it is estimated that such an event occurs once every 400–2400 years (Brehm et al., 2022). There is compelling evidence that Miyake events are caused by extreme solar particle events, likely related to super-flares discovered on solar-like stars (Cliver et al., 2022; Maehara et al., 2012; Usoskin and Kovaltsov, 2012; Usoskin et al., 2013). The inferred flare size for these events was approximately 10^{34} erg, about 20 times larger than the bolometric energy estimated for a Carrington-class flare (Miyake et al., 2014). However, intriguing complexities introduce some doubt as to whether these events are indeed extreme solar events or if they could result from a nearby supernova (Miyake et al., 2012) or even a gamma-ray burst (Hambaryan and Neuhäuser, 2013). Table B.1 in Appendix B compiles a comprehensive list of significant geomagnetic storm occurrences witnessed by humanity, spanning from 12400 BCE to February 2022.

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date

Date	Event Description
12400-12399 BCE	Probable Miyake Event and speculated to be the largest known, potentially twice the magnitude of the 774-775 event (Bard et al., 2023).
7176 BCE	Discovered through a spike in ^{10}Be in ice cores, this event was unexpectedly observed near a Solar minimum and is estimated to be as strong as, or slightly stronger than, the famous 774–775 CE event (Brehm et al., 2022; Paleari et al., 2022).
5410 BCE	Rapid increase of ^{14}C concentration in tree rings. Based on data from California, Switzerland, and Finland (Miyake et al., 2021).
5259 BCE	Discovered through a spike in ^{10}Be in ice cores, this event was at least as strong as the 774–775 event (Brehm et al., 2022).
660 BCE	Notable surge in ^{10}Be within Greenland ice cores, this too exhibited a magnitude comparable to that of the 774–775 event (Hayakawa et al., 2019b; O’Hare et al., 2019).
774–775 CE	This extreme solar proton event, the first identified Miyake event, caused the largest and most rapid rise in ^{14}C levels ever recorded (Cliver et al., 2020; Mekhaldi et al., 2015; Melott and Thomas, 2012; Miyake et al., 2012; Reimer et al., 2020; Usoskin et al., 2013).
993–994 CE	This event caused a ^{14}C spike visible in tree rings, which was used to date Viking archaeological remains in L’Anse aux Meadows in Newfoundland to 1021 (Hayakawa et al., 2016; Kuitems et al., 2021; Mekhaldi et al., 2015; Miyake et al., 2013).
1052 CE	Discovered through a carbon-14 spike along with the 1279 (Brehm et al., 2021).
1279 CE	The record reveals two new Miyake event (1052CE and 1279CE), indicating that strong solar events that might be harmful to modern electronic systems probably occur more frequently than previously thought (Brehm et al., 2021).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
March 6-8, 1582	Great magnetic storms of March 1582, caused a prolonged severe-extreme geomagnetic storm, leading to auroras visible up to 28.8° MLAT and ~ 33.0° ILAT (Hattori et al., 2019; Sánchez Carrasco and Vaquero, 2020).
February 15, 1730	At least as intense as the 1989 event but less intense than the Carrington event. Historical records from East Asia document 29 instances of auroras, alongside 37 observations of sunspots (Hayakawa et al., 2018).
September 17, 1770	Sunspot drawings and zenith-reaching red auroras at Kyoto, Japan hint at a storm rivaling 1859's Carrington event. Lasted nearly nine nights, with auroral displays appearing in low magnetic latitude areas (Ebihara et al., 2017; Hayakawa et al., 2017; Kataoka and Iwahashi, 2017).
September 2, 1859	The Carrington event (Discussed in section B.1)
February 4, 1872	The Chapman–Silverman storm (Discussed in section B.2)
November 17, 1882	The “Electric Storm”, occurred during the extended period of strong geomagnetic activity in solar cycle 12, had gained notoriety for the observation of an unusual “auroral beam” by astronomer Edward Walter Maunder and John Rand Capron from Guildown, Surrey (Capron, 1883; Love, 2018).
October 31, 1903	The most notable storm documented during any solar minimum period, emerging during the acceding minimum phase of Solar Cycle 14. Estimated to have reached a Dst value of approximately -531 nT and was triggered by a rapid CME with an average velocity of about 1500 km/s. Aurora sightings were conservatively reported up to approximately $\sim 44.1^\circ$ ILAT, accompanied by widespread disruptions and overcharging of telegraph systems (Hayakawa et al., 2020).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
September 25, 1909	The estimated Dst is -595 nT, resembling the March 1989 incident. Was instigated by an interplanetary CME traveling at an average velocity of about 1,679 km/s from the Sun to Earth. The initial pressure exerted on the magnetopause was approximately 32.4 nPa, resulting in the compression of the subsolar magnetopause radius to roughly 5.9 Earth radii (Love et al., 2019b).
May 12, 1921	The New York Railroad storm (Discussed in section B.3)
January 25-26, 1938	Eight months after solar cycle 17's peak in April 1937, the "Fatima storm" occurred, believed by some Catholics to fulfill a prophecy from Sister Lúcia Santos. Lúcia, with her cousins, claimed visions known as Our Lady of Fátima, revealing three secrets. The second, predicting World War II's start, mentioned an unknown light as a sign of divine punishment. Lúcia later linked the aurora borealis during the storm to this prophecy, sparking debate on its supernatural or natural origins (Nature, 1938a,b,c).
March 24, 1940	Linked to the most substantial storm sudden commencement (SSC) documented by the Service on Rapid Magnetic Variations (SRMV) between 1869 and 2020, it resulted in significant disruption to communication systems in the United States (Hayakawa et al., 2021; Love et al., 2023).
September 18-19, 1941	Amid the rise of radio and electrical technology in daily life and the backdrop of World War II, a significant historical juncture, its impact heightened awareness both in the scientific community and among the public (Love and Coïsson, 2016; McNish, 1941).
March 27, 1946	Occurred during the ascending phase of Solar Cycle 18, with the equatorial boundary of the auroral oval extending to $\sim 41.8^\circ$ ILAT, resulting in a corona aurora in Watheroo, Australia. Estimated Dst reached -512 nT (Hayakawa et al., 2020; Love, 2021).
February 23, 1956	Propelled by solar energetic particles, the ground-level enhancement of solar cosmic ray intensity (GLE05) stands out as the most renowned among the observed proton events dating back to 1942 (Belov et al., 2005; Meyer et al., 1956; Usoskin et al., 2020).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
September 13, 1957	The earliest among the five most intense superstorms observed since the International Geophysical Year (IGY) from July 1, 1957, with a Dst of -427 nT. The calculation of Dst also commenced in Kyoto from January 1, 1957 (Stanislawska et al., 2018).
February 10-11, 1958	Ranked among the five most intense superstorms since IGY, with a Dst of -426 nT (Lanzerotti and Baker, 2018; Stanislawska et al., 2018).
July 15, 1959	Another one of the top five most intense superstorms since IGY, with a Dst of -429 nT (Stanislawska et al., 2018).
May 23, 1967	During the Cold War, polar surveillance radar blackouts led the U.S. military to prepare for nuclear war until confirming the solar origin. This event, occurring during the rapid rise of solar cycle 20, highlighted the need for the U.S. Air Force to recognize space environment effects, fostering the establishment of a forecasting system and expanding efforts into space weather monitoring and prediction (Knipp et al., 2016).
October 31, 1968	Dst reached -224 nT. The auroral arc persisted for over 12 hours and shifted southward during the night (Laurie and Leaton, 1969; Roble et al., 1970).
August 4, 1972	Recorded as the fastest transit time of a CME, this event stands out as one of the most extreme solar particle events (SPE) during the Space Age, posing significant hazards to human spaceflight. It resulted in severe technological disruptions and even caused the accidental detonation of numerous sea mines in the south of Hai Phong, North Vietnam (Knipp et al., 2018).
March 13-14, 1989	The most severe storm of the Space Age, registering an exceptionally low Dst value of -589 nT (Bolduc, 2002; Love et al., 2022; Stanislawska et al., 2018).
November 8, 1991	A powerful solar storm with Dst -354 nT and approximately half the energy of the March 1989 event occurred, resulting in auroras visible in the United States as far south as Texas (McEwen and Huang, 1995).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
April 6, 2000	With a Dst of -288 nT, this event serves as evidence of plasma enhancement after sunset (Katamzi-Joseph et al., 2017).
July 14, 2000	The onset of the storm coincided with Bastille Day, the national day of France, hence referred to as the Bastille Day storm. Following the detection of a solar flare, a halo CME reached Earth on July 15. Although the storm couldn't caused major damage to power transformers and satellites, it recorded a peak Dst of -301 nT (Andrews, 2001; Reiner et al., 2001; Tsurutani et al., 2006; Watari et al., 2001; Webber et al., 2002).
April 11, 2001	A solar flare originating from a sunspot region linked to this event, occurring before this timeframe, generated the most substantial flare observed during the Space Age, measuring approximately X20. This flare, the first to saturate spaceborne monitoring instruments (a record surpassed in 2003), was directed away from Earth (Katamzi-Joseph et al., 2017).
November 6, 2001	A rapid CME induced vibrant auroras visible as far south as Texas, California, and Florida, resulting in a substantial Dst drop to -292 nT (Alex et al., 2005; Mishin et al., 2007).
October 29-30 2003	One of the most severe series of storms of the Space Age, with a peak Dst of -353 nT and auroras observed as far south as Texas and the Mediterranean countries of Europe, occurred during a series of solar storms from mid-October to early November 2003, commonly known as the Halloween solar storms (Brodrick et al., 2005; Love, 2021; Thomson et al., 2005, 2004; Tsurutani et al., 2006; Xue et al., 2023; Zinke, 2023).
November 20, 2003	One of the strongest among the five most intense superstorms observed since the International Geophysical Year (IGY), with a Dst of -422 nT, topping the charts of the last three decades. This superstorm was linked to a high-speed CME and the estimated storm maximum intensity value (Dst_m) reached a -533 nT (Gonzalez, 2022; Grechnev et al., 2014; Love, 2021; Meier et al., 2005; Roy and Nandy, 2023; Srivastava et al., 2009; Stanislawska et al., 2018).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
July 23, 2012	An exceptionally rapid CME moving away from Earth, possessing qualities that suggest it could potentially be classified as a Carrington-level event (Baker et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2014; Ngwira et al., 2013; Riley and Love, 2017; Russell et al., 2013; Zhu et al., 2016).
October 14, 2014	A comprehensive study tracked a coronal mass ejection (CME) as it traveled an impressive distance of up to 111 astronomical units (AU), involving multiple spacecraft. Initially, Sun-monitoring probes like PROBA2 (ESA), Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (ESA/NASA), and Solar Dynamics Observatory (NASA) observed its departure from the Sun. At 1 AU, STEREO-A directly witnessed its effects, with additional data from ESA's Venus Express. By October 17, the CME reached Mars, where missions like Mars Express, MAVEN, Mars Odyssey, and Mars Science Laboratory detected it. On October 22, at 3.1 AU, the CME intersected with comet 67P/Churyumov–Gerasimenko, aligning with the Sun and Mars, and was observed by the Rosetta mission. By November 12, at 9.9 AU, Cassini observed the CME approaching Saturn. New Horizons, en route to Pluto at 31.6 AU, potentially captured data about the CME three months after its eruption. Voyager 2's records indicated the CME's passage approximately 17 months later. Additionally, the Curiosity rover's Radiation Assessment Detector (RAD), along with instruments on Mars Odyssey, Rosetta, and Cassini, detected a Forbush decrease, indicating the CME's protective magnetic field (Witasse et al., 2017).
March 17-18, 2015	A strong geomagnetic storm, the largest in solar cycle 24 with a Dst of -223 nT, occurred unexpectedly without significant precursor solar flares. It was triggered by a sudden variation in the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF), catching space weather agencies around the world off guard. Due to its date of occurrence, it is also commonly known as the St. Patrick's Day storm (Astafyeva et al., 2015; Chaurasiya et al., 2022; Jacobsen and Andalsvik, 2016; Kamide and Kusano, 2015; Maurya et al., 2018).

Table B.1 Quick overview of significant space weather events till date (continued)

Date	Event Description
February 3-4, 2022	A mild geomagnetic storm led to the failure of 38 SpaceX Starlink satellites launched into low Earth orbit (LEO) (Baruah et al., 2024; Berger et al., 2023; Dang et al., 2022; Duann et al., 2023; Fang et al., 2022; Gopalswamy et al., 2023; Guarnieri et al., 2023; Gulyaeva et al., 2023; He et al., 2023; Kataoka et al., 2022; Laskar et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2022; Lockwood et al., 2023; Pal et al., 2023; Tsurutani et al., 2022; Tsyganenko et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022).

Appendix C

Brief understanding of the interior and magnetic activity of the Sun

C.1 Core

At the core of the Sun, positioned at its center, lies a dense and intensely hot region, extending about one-fourth of the way to its surface. This nearly $1/64^{th}$ fraction of the Sun's volume holds approximately half of the Sun's mass, making it exceptionally dense, estimated at 150 grams per cubic centimeter – about seven times denser than osmium, the densest metal known. Temperatures in the core soar to around 15 million degrees Kelvin, with pressures reaching an estimated 26.5 million gigapascals. At such extreme conditions, particles exhibit an average kinetic energy of about 2 kilo-electron volts (keV), surpassing all ionization energies. Consequently, particles within the core are either electrons or fully ionized bare nuclei. The probability of penetration for the reaction between two protons, crucial for initiating the proton-proton chain, is approximately 10^{-9} . Whereas, the average energy level of 2 keV ensures the presence of a sufficient number of energetic particles in the high-energy tail of the distribution, overcoming the repulsive electrostatic forces between hydrogen nuclei. Thus, the Sun's core functions as an efficient fusion reactor, where hydrogen fuel undergoes fusion to produce helium nuclei.

The theory proposing proton–proton chain (pp chain) reactions as the fundamental mechanism driving the Sun's and other stars' energy production was postulated by Arthur Eddington in the 1920s. In 1939, Hans Bethe calculated the rates of various reactions in stars. Beginning with the combination of two protons to form a deuterium nucleus and a positron

Figure C.1 Reaction scheme of the proton-proton branch I, II, and III respectively.

(Fig. C.1), Bethe identified what is now recognized as Branch II of the pp chain.¹ There are four possible branches of pp chains and the overall reaction goes as:

Notably, out of the energy generated, approximately 2.2% (or about 0.59 MeV) is lost to the neutrinos produced. Nonetheless, nearly 99% of the Sun's energy output originates from various p-p chains, with the remainder coming from the CNO cycle.² Ultimately, a small fraction (0.7%) of the original particles' mass is converted to energy, and this energy, in the form of radiation (X-ray, gamma rays), diffuses outward into the Sun's outer layers through the radiation zone.

C.2 Radiative zone

The radiative zone within the Sun extends to about 72.5% of the solar radius from the core boundary. Energy transport through the core and radiative zone occurs through photon diffusion. Gamma rays and X-rays undergo scattering, absorption, and re-emission multiple times as they gradually traverse the radiative zone until reaching its outer edge. As these photons are re-emitted, they acquire longer wavelengths and lower energies. Consequently, the radiative zone maintains a temperature gradient profile given by

¹This research formed part of Bethe's work in stellar nucleosynthesis, for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1967.

²Sometimes referred to as the Bethe-Weizsäcker cycle, named after Hans Albrecht Bethe and Carl Friedrich von Weizsäcker, it is believed to dominate in stars more than 1.3 times the mass of the Sun.

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dr}\right)_{\text{radiative}} = -K_T(r) \frac{\rho(r)}{T(r)^3} \frac{L(r)}{4\pi r^2},$$

where $K_T(r)$ is a multiplication factor depending on the optical properties of the solar interior, $\rho(r)$ is the density of the radiative zone, $T(r)$ is the temperature, and $L(r)$ is the outward energy flow rate as a function of radial distance from the center (r). Since the majority of energy production occurs deep within the core, energy flow can be considered constant (represented by solar luminosity or L_\odot) beyond approximately $0.3 R_\odot$.

C.3 Convective zone

Above the radiative zone is the convective zone, where energy moves outward through the movement of solar materials. The transition layer between the radiative and convective zones, known as the tachocline, is located at $0.675 - 0.725 R_\odot$ and exhibits significant shear due to the differing rotation speeds of the zones (Spiegel and Weiss, 1980; van Ballegoijen, 1982). The convective zone experiences a rapid decrease in temperature with increasing altitude, dropping from approximately 2000000K to 5700K at the solar surface (or photosphere, precisely). In the convective zone, the radiative temperature gradient exceeds the adiabatic temperature gradient (or adiabatic lapse rate). If the temperature difference is too steep, it leads to instability for convection, surpassing the temperature change caused by matter rising adiabatically, without gaining or losing heat³. Consequently, convection overrides the radiative process, making convective energy transfer the primary mechanism for plasma, where energy primarily moves through the motion of large plasma cells instead of photon diffusion to maintain the rapid decrease in temperature gradient. We can estimate the temperature gradient in the convective region by assuming negligible magnetic field effects and slow cell motion, ensuring the thermodynamic process is adiabatic; which goes as:

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dr}\right)_{\text{adiabatic}} = -\frac{2}{5} G \frac{\bar{m}}{\kappa} \frac{M(r)}{r^2}.$$

Here, \bar{m} represents the mean molecular mass of the local plasma, κ and G are the Boltzmann and gravitational constants, and $M(r)$ is the mass of the Sun up to the radius r .

³known as the Schwarzschild stability criterion for the solar atmosphere

C.4 Solar atmosphere

The solar atmosphere stretches from the solar surface⁴ of the Sun to theoretically the end of the heliosphere. It consists of several layers: the photosphere, the chromosphere, the transition region, and the corona.

Figure C.2 The graphic shows simulated solar energy across different parts of the spectrum, both at the top of the atmosphere (ToA) and on Earth's surface. It includes ultraviolet (UV), visible, near-infrared (NIR), and shortwave infrared (SWIR) regions. The dashed line at the top marks the typical range covered by solar spectral irradiance (SSI). Additionally, it highlights areas where atmospheric components like ozone (O_3), oxygen (O_2), water vapor (H_2O), carbon dioxide (CO_2), and methane (CH_4) absorb solar radiation. Graphics created by Luke Ellison and NASA.

The **photosphere** is like the Sun's surface when seen by naked-eye or by white-light observations. Being the bottommost layer of the solar atmosphere, it stretches up from the surface to approximately 500 kilometers where the temperature is at its lowest. Thereby, It's a comperably thin layer, which is mad of neutral gas and where 99% of the Sun's light and heat come from. Since the gas in the photosphere absorbs and then emits radiation similarly to a blackbody, the photosphere effectively emits a continuous spectrum resembling that of a blackbody (See Fig. C.2). The temperature of this emission spectrum is approximately 5,762 Kelvin.

⁴The solar surface is determined by where the optical depth of a photon with a wavelength of 5000 equals 1, indicating the point where the probability of a photon escaping from this surface is $1/e$.

Figure C.3 The picture shows the inside of the Sun and its outer layers, called the solar atmosphere. It also points out some basic things happening on the Sun using pictures from the SOHO spacecraft. Image Credit: ESA and NASA/SOHO.

The **chromosphere** is a layer of glowing gas extending several thousand kilometers above the photosphere. Its temperature rises from about 4,300 K to 10,000 K due to the absorption of acoustic waves originating from the convection zone. Unlike the photosphere, where energy input mainly comes from radiation, in the chromosphere, the primary energy source is the absorption of mechanical energy. The density in the chromosphere is even lower than that of the photosphere. It allows most visible light to pass through, only revealing itself in narrow atomic lines. However, it becomes optically thick in specific atomic transition lines, such as the red $H\alpha$ line (6563) or ultraviolet lines of elements like calcium (Ca^+). The mechanism responsible for heating the chromosphere is still debated, but shock wave dissipation is the most probable explanation. It's thought that turbulence in the photosphere generates acoustic waves that travel outward into regions of lower density. As they propagate, these waves transform into shocks, releasing their energy into the chromosphere and the corona.

The **transition region** refers to a thin and highly irregular layer within the Sun's atmosphere, acting as a boundary between the intense heat of the corona and the significantly cooler chromosphere. Heat transfers downward from the corona to the chromosphere, giving rise to this narrow zone where temperatures rapidly shift from 10^6 K to approximately 10^4 K. At such extreme temperatures, hydrogen becomes ionized, making it challenging to detect. Instead, the emission in the transition region primarily stems from ions like C^{3+} , O^{3+} , and Si^{3+} , emitting light in the ultraviolet part of the solar spectrum, detectable only from space. Consequently, extensive research on the transition region has been conducted using space-based observatories.

Figure C.4 The images show eclipsed helmet streamers, which are elongated bright structures in the corona of the Sun. These structures appear wider near the solar surface but taper into slender spikes. The **left** image was captured by Adrien Mauduit during the total solar eclipse on July 2, 2019, visible from Chile, Argentina, and a large part of South America. The **middle** image displays the white-light corona observed by the K-coronagraph (K-Cor) instrument at the Mauna Loa Solar Observatory (MLSO) during the same eclipse. The **right** image represents a simulated coronal structure predicted by the Predictive Solar Surface Flux Transport (PSSFT) model developed at the Center of Excellence in Space Sciences India (CESSI) (Bhowmik and Nandy, 2018). These streamers often surround darker cavities where bright prominences may be visible. Their brightness is a result of higher density regions and enhanced scattering of solar radiation. Coronal intensity tends to decrease near the poles, especially during solar maximum. These findings, along with the predictions, can be accessed at <http://www.cessi.in/solareclipse2019/>.

The **corona** (from the Latin for 'crown') represents the outermost and least dense layer of the solar atmosphere, extending over vast distances and eventually merging with the solar wind. Typically, the corona is observable solely through ground-based coronagraphs or even with the naked eye during total solar eclipses when the Moon obscures the bright photosphere, causing the sky to darken. Under normal conditions, the corona appears much fainter compared to the bright sky, except in proximity to the Sun in certain emission lines

(See Fig. C.4). However, nowadays, advanced coronagraphs on space-based observatories, simulating artificial eclipses, enable daily observation of this intriguing region of the solar atmosphere (Lyot, 1939).

The corona is characterized by extremely high temperatures, reaching a few million degrees, and comprises low-density, fully ionized plasma. Despite its prominence, the heating mechanism of the corona remains poorly understood, necessitating further research. The Skylab mission revealed extended dark regions in X-ray solar images, known as coronal holes, characterized by low-density cold plasma and unipolar magnetic fields. These holes cover about 20% of the solar surface during solar minimum, with polar coronal holes being permanent features while lower latitude holes endure for several solar rotations. Coronal holes are associated with open coronal field lines, facilitating the rapid outward expansion of coronal plasma along these lines, which significantly reduces plasma density, appearing as darker regions in X-ray images. The development of coronal holes throughout the solar cycle closely aligns with the evolution of the Sun's magnetic fields.

In 1910, British astrophysicist Arthur Eddington hinted at the existence of what we now call the solar wind, albeit indirectly, in a footnote within an article about Comet Morehouse (Durham, 2006). Although Eddington had previously suggested a similar idea during a Royal Institution address the year before, where he proposed that the expelled material comprised electrons, his examination of Comet Morehouse led him to believe that they were ions (Durham, 2006). By the 1930s, scientists inferred that the solar corona's temperature must reach a million degrees Celsius due to its extension into space, as observed during total solar eclipses. Subsequent spectroscopic analysis validated this remarkable temperature. In the mid-1950s, British mathematician Sydney Chapman calculated the characteristics of gas at such high temperatures, determining that the corona, being an excellent conductor of heat, must extend far beyond Earth's orbit (Akasofu, 1970). Around the same time, German astronomer Ludwig Franz Benedikt Biermann observed that a comet's tail consistently points away from the Sun, regardless of the comet's direction of travel. Biermann proposed that this phenomenon occurs due to a continuous stream of particles emitted by the Sun, pushing the comet's tail away from the Sun (Biermann, 1951). However, in a recent study, Schröder (2008) pointed out that German astronomers Paul Ahnert and Cuno Hoffmeister should be attributed as the first to link the solar wind to the direction of a comet's tail based on observations of the comet Whipple–Fedke (1942g; Ahnert, 1943; Hoffmeister, 1943). Nevertheless, in the late fifties, American astrophysicist Eugene Newman Parker unified Chapman's model of heat flow from the Sun and Biermann's hypothesis of the comet tail's deflection by coining the term “solar wind.”

C.5 Solar magnetic activity

Just a few years after the detection of the magnetic field in Sun, J. Larmor, an Irish physicist, and mathematician, directed the focus of the astronomical community towards the notion that the primary method of generating solar magnetic fields, as evidenced by the observations, likely involved electromagnetic induction within the moving, electrically conductive solar substances (Larmor, 1919a,b). This concept drew parallels to the mechanisms operating within the contemporary pinnacle of human engineering, the automobile dynamo engine, hence earning the moniker “dynamo theory.” Subsequently, with years of research, it became evident that these strong magnetic fields impede convective energy transport from beneath the surface, naturally resulting in the lower temperatures observed within sunspots compared to the surrounding photosphere. Such revelations underscore the intricate interplay between magnetic fields and solar phenomena, emphasizing the profound fascination inherent in scientific inquiry (Charbonneau, 2020).

Explaining the intricacies of solar dynamo physics could fill an entire thesis due to its complexity. Thereby, here’s a simplified overview (refer to Fig. C.5 for detailed understanding), which starts with the assumption that initially, the Sun poises a north-south magnetic field resembling a dipole. As its rotation varies across latitudes – the equator spins faster (25 days/rotation) than the poles (33 days/rotation), the velocity difference causes this north-south magnetic field to stretch toward the equator, forming an additional toroidal field component. These fields, opposite in each hemisphere, intensify at the tachocline, where magnetic buoyancy is suppressed, and strong radial shear exists (Spiegel and Weiss, 1980; van Ballegoijen, 1982). When strong magnetic tubes emerge from this layer into the convection zone, the ‘ Ω ’-shaped loops containing magnetized plasma rise to the photosphere due to magnetic buoyancy. The footpoints of these loops, known as sunspots, exhibit concentrated magnetic field regions (with intensities around 1000 Gauss or 0.1 T) and appear as dark spots in white light (Cliver and Herbst, 2018; Parker, 1955). Sunspots form because the strong magnetic field inhibits plasma motion upward, resulting in lower temperatures. As the centers of solar magnetic activity, sunspots are termed solar active regions (ARs). One sunspot exhibits an outward-pointing magnetic field, while its counterpart displays an inward-pointing field. Due to the opposing toroidal fields in each hemisphere of the Sun, sunspot pairs manifest different orientations in the northern and southern halves. The Coriolis force causes the ascending magnetic tubes to tilt progressively as they rise, particularly pronounced at higher solar latitudes (known as Joy’s Law; Hale et al., 1919). Consequently, the following section of the tilted tube possesses a magnetic polarity distinct from its originating pole. Eventually, these tilted sunspot pairs diminish near equator, and their magnetic influence disperses throughout the Sun due to meridional circulation. This circulation gener-

Figure C.5 Diagram illustrating solar dynamo processes: (a) Poloidal field sheared by the Sun's differential rotation near the bottom of the convection zone. (b) Formation of toroidal field due to differential rotation. (c) Buoyant loops rising to the surface, twisting as they ascend, forming sunspots. (d, e, f) Emergence and spread of additional flux from decaying spots. (g) Meridional flow carrying surface magnetic flux poleward, causing polar field reversal. (h) Some flux transported downward and toward the equator. (i) Reversal of poloidal flux through shearing near the bottom, producing new toroidal field with opposite sign. Image courtesy: NCAR/HAO.

ates a new north-south magnetic field at the poles, supplanting the previous one and initiating a fresh cycle (Nandy and Choudhuri, 2002). This cyclical process induces fluctuations in the Sun's overall magnetic field, referred to as a solar cycle, spanning approximately 11 years (Fig. C.6). Throughout various phases of this cycle, the behavior of the Sun's magnetic

field varies. During periods when it predominantly adopts a dipolar configuration, the Sun enters a quieter phase known as the solar minimum. Conversely, when the toroidal field configuration becomes dominant, the Sun enters the solar maximum phase, characterized by increased sunspots and solar activity.

SILSO graphics (<http://sidc.be/silso>) Royal Observatory of Belgium 2024 March 1

Figure C.6 The figure depicts the monthly mean sunspot number (shown in blue) alongside the 13-month smoothed monthly sunspot number (represented in red) for the past five solar cycles. This image was generated by WDC-SILSO, which is managed by the Royal Observatory of Belgium in Brussels.

As a flux tube emerges above the photosphere, it enters the chromosphere where the emission line spectrum predominates. In particular, within the $H\alpha$ emission line, ARs appear brighter than quieter regions. The chromosphere also hosts dark structures known as filaments, comprised of cool, dense material suspended against gravity by magnetic tension (Vial and Engvold, 2015). Filaments are a prominent feature of the chromosphere, appearing bright against the dark background at the solar limb and known as prominences. Extending beyond the chromosphere into the corona, flux tubes associated with ARs manifest as luminous and dynamic structures termed coronal loops, observable in extreme ultraviolet (EUV) wavelengths (Reale, 2014). Occasionally, coronagraph observations reveal cap-like coronal structures with elongated peaks, identified as helmet streamers (Wang et al., 2000). Another significant feature of the solar corona is the coronal hole (Cranmer, 2009), typically located

at the Sun's poles during solar minimum periods. These regions exhibit open magnetic field lines and appear dark in EUV wavelengths (See Fig. C.3).

Appendix D

The intrinsic magnetic field of Earth

Nearly two centuries ago, in 1839, the German mathematician and physicist Carl Friedrich Gauss demonstrated that Earth's magnetic field could be described as the gradient of a scalar potential:

$$\mathbf{B} = -\nabla\phi = \nabla(\phi_{\text{internal}} + \phi_{\text{external}}),$$

where ϕ_{internal} represents the scalar potential due to sources within Earth, and ϕ_{external} is attributed to external sources. Gauss hypothesized that an electrically conducting region of the atmosphere – what we now recognize as the ionosphere – could explain such external variations in the magnetic field.¹ Gauss, along with his colleague Weber, established a network of magnetic observatories worldwide. Their collected data illustrated that Earth's surface field was primarily internal and predominantly dipolar. This dipolar nature greatly simplifies the treatment of the terrestrial magnetosphere.

The Earth's dipole magnetic moment is tilted approximately 11° to the rotation axis, with a present-day moment of about $7.8 \times 10^{15} \text{ T} \cdot \text{m}^3$ or $30.2 \mu\text{T} \cdot R_E^3$. However, this dipole moment and its orientation are not constant; they undergo significant variations, including occasional reversals, over time scales spanning hundreds of thousands of years or more. On top of that, tilted dipole moment rotates with the planet and may vary in orientation relative to the solar wind flow throughout the day. While the magnetic field near the planet may deviate from a dipolar shape where the solar wind and magnetic field are not in pressure balance, the internal planetary field typically dominates charged-particle motion, especially when the magnetic moment is strong. Therefore, the dipole approximation of the magnetic field often proves useful and in spherical coordinates it can be described by,

¹Refer to the English translation of Carl Friedrich Gauss's *Allgemeine Theorie des Erdmagnetismus*, published in 1839 in the *Resultate aus den Beobachtungen des Magnetischen Vereins im Jahre 1838* (Glassmeier and Tsurutani, 2014).

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_r &= 2Mr^{-3} \cos \theta, \\
 B_\theta &= Mr^{-3} \sin \theta, \\
 |B| &= Mr^{-3}(1 + 3 \cos^2 \theta)^{1/2},
 \end{aligned}$$

where θ represents the magnetic colatitude, and M is the dipole magnetic moment. In this coordinate system aligned with the dipole, there is no B_ϕ component.

D.1 Regions of the magnetosphere

The following are the relevant terminologies and regions of the magnetosphere that play a role in the context of Earth's space environment and adverse space weather.

The bow shock: In the stream of the solar wind, Earth with its magnetic field acts as a barrier. Similar to water flowing around a rock in a stream, the solar wind is diverted around the magnetosphere. However, the typical speed of the solar wind as it approaches Earth is around 400 km/s, which surpasses the speeds of typical waves in the solar wind, such as the fast magnetosonic speed. Both the sonic and Alfvénic Mach numbers are typically large, on the order of 10^2 .² Consequently, a shock forms upstream of the obstacle – known as the bow shock. This shock, technically termed a “fast mode” or “switch-on” shock, causes the flow to abruptly decelerate over a short distance, comparable to the ion gyroradius for the solar wind, thereby separating the free streaming solar wind from the region where the presence of Earth's magnetic field significantly modifies the space environment. Simultaneously, there is a notable ‘jump’ in plasma density, temperature, and magnetic field strength along the shock boundary. In terms of normal and tangent components across the boundary and with the usual notations, jump parameters goes as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{\text{normal}} &= \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma + 1} V_{\text{SW}_{\text{normal}}}, \\
 V_{\text{tangent}} &= \frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \frac{B_{\text{SW}_{\text{normal}}} B_{\text{SW}_{\text{tangent}}}}{\mu_0 \rho_{\text{SW}} V_{\text{SW}}} + V_{\text{SW}_{\text{tangent}}}, \\
 B_{\text{normal}} &= 0, \\
 B_{\text{tangent}} &= \frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} B_{\text{SW}_{\text{tangent}}},
 \end{aligned}$$

²The sonic Mach number, often only Mach, is a dimensionless quantity in fluid dynamics representing the ratio of flow velocity past a boundary to the local speed of sound. An Alfvén Mach number is such a ratio with the speed of Alfvén waves or the transverse waves along magnetic field lines within the plasma, rather than with its sound speed.

$$\rho = \frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} \rho_{SW},$$

$$p = \frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \rho_{SW} V_{SW_{normal}}^2.$$

Considering the solar wind to be an ideal monatomic gas ($\gamma = \frac{5}{3}$), for wind speeds greatly exceeding the magnetosonic speed, the solar wind velocity decreases by a factor of 4, while both the density and magnetic field strength increase by the same factor, 4. The gas pressure, on the other hand, becomes three-fourths of the solar wind (Gombosi, 1998, Chapter 14). Due to the shape of the magnetosphere, the shock takes on a curved form, resembling a characteristic bow shape.

The magnetopause: The equations for bow shock jump conditions, delineate the ratio of change in parameters at the shock boundary but do not define its precise location. The bow shock's position is chiefly determined by the configuration and dimensions of the magnetospheric "obstacle," known as the magnetopause. In a simplified model, the dayside magnetopause can be regarded as a tangential discontinuity that is continuously influenced by the constantly fluctuating solar wind. This discontinuity arises when the tangential component of the magnetic field, as well as the density and pressure, exhibit discontinuities across a thin transitional layer. The magnetopause acts as the boundary separating the shocked solar wind from the region influenced by Earth's magnetic dipole field. At a tangential discontinuity, there is no plasma transport across the boundary, and the normal component of the magnetic field vanishes. Simultaneously, the tangential magnetic field component, density, and pressure may all display discontinuities (Gombosi, 1998, Chapter 6). However, the total pressure (combining thermal and magnetic components) is balanced at the magnetopause. Within the magnetopause, the total pressure is primarily dictated by the compressed terrestrial dipole field, rendering the thermal pressure negligible. Conversely, outside the magnetopause, the total pressure arises from a combination of thermal and magnetic pressures from the shocked solar wind. The flanks of magnetopause typically exhibit supersonic and super-Alfvénic characteristics and are thicker compared to the dayside magnetopause (Haaland et al., 2019). In a preliminary approximation, disregarding the contribution from the tangential magnetic field component of the solar wind, the pressure balance condition yields:

$$\rho_{SW} V_{SW_{normal}}^2 = \mathcal{F} \frac{B_{Earth}^2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{R_{Eq}}{R_{MP}} \right)^6$$

Here, \mathcal{F} represents a magnetic field compression factor (approximately 2), B_{eq} denotes the equatorial magnetic field at Earth's surface, and R_{MP} signifies the standoff distance of the magnetopause – the distance from Earth's center to the nose of the magnetopause.

Figure D.1 **A** Schematic illustration of the dayside, low-latitude magnetopause region during continuous reconnection under southward interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) conditions (view from dusk). The magnetopause is identified as a current layer of RD-type. Here, magnetosheath particles can either rebound from the magnetopause, entering the magnetosheath boundary layer (MSBL) – the immediate outer layer of the boundary, or traverse the magnetopause and enter the low-latitude boundary layer (LLBL) – the immediate inner layer of the boundary. Conversely, magnetospheric particles can either rebound from the magnetopause, entering the LLBL, or traverse the magnetopause and enter the MSBL. Image courtesy of Hasegawa (2012), originally produced by Gosling et al. (1990) Panel **B** illustrates the magnetopause reconnection site. White areas on the left and right exhibit magnetic fields pointing in opposite directions, with the northward-pointing magnetosphere on the right and the southward pointing magnetosheath on the left. During reconnection, there is a flow toward the magnetopause, carrying the reconnecting magnetic fields inward. The dominant contribution to the electric field in this region is the $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ term, generating an electric field in the y direction, known as the reconnection electric field. Further details include the formation of ion and electron dissipation regions, marked by the absence of plasma transport across magnetic fields. The Hall magnetic field, observed in the magnetosphere, confirms the collisionless reconnection model. Additionally, the electron dissipation region, where reconnected magnetic fields can break and cross-connect, plays a crucial role in reconnection dynamics. This region, depicted by the inner rectangle, has a thickness much smaller than the ion dissipation region and is characterized by accelerated electrons and outflow jets. The Hall electric field, produced by the bulk flow of electrons, points toward the magnetopause on either side, illustrating the complex dynamics of reconnection at the dayside magnetopause. The green arrow indicates a possible polar trajectory of spacecraft observing magnetospheric plasma processes. Image is reproduced from Cassak and Fuselier (2016).

This expression can be readily evaluated. Under typical solar wind conditions, $R_{MP} \approx 8 \sim 10R_E$. Empirically, the ratio $(R_{BS} - R_{MP})/R_{MP}$ has been found to be 1.1 times the density ratio across the bow shock boundary, which is approximately 4 for a strong shock. Consequently, $R_{BS} \approx 1.275R_{MP} \approx 10 \sim 13R_E$. Here R_{BS} is the subsolar distance of the bow shock from the center of Earth. This finding aligns with the predictions of the hypersonic approximation.

It is worth noting that the dayside magnetopause, holds a significant importance in space weather studies, particularly for being a key reconnection location within the magnetosphere (Cassak and Fuselier, 2016; Lavraud et al., 2011; Trattner et al., 2021). Magnetic reconnection is a fundamental process occurring within electrically conducting plasmas, wherein the magnetic topology undergoes rearrangement, converting magnetic energy into kinetic energy, thermal energy, and particle acceleration (The underlying physics is elaborated upon in the subsequent subsection). One notable aspect is its proximity to Earth, making it the natural site where reconnection occurs most prominently. Being accessible to in-situ measurements through satellite observations, it offers the opportunity for detailed observational studies surpassing any other naturally occurring reconnection scenario. In conjunction with focused laboratory investigations of reconnection, its exploration in magnetically confined fusion devices, theoretical and numerical analyses, and remote observations of the Sun, other planetary magnetospheres, and the heliosphere, significant progress has been made in understanding the reconnection process. A second crucial aspect of dayside reconnection lies in its direct influence on Earth, particularly its role in space weather. In an idealized scenario devoid of reconnection, the transfer of material and energy from interplanetary space to the magnetosphere would be minimal, with Earth's magnetic field primarily shielding it from charged particles in space (Cassak and Fuselier, 2016; Trattner et al., 2021). However, reconnection alters this scenario fundamentally: by altering the connectivity of magnetic fields, reconnection actively facilitates the transfer of material and energy from interplanetary space to the magnetosphere (see Fig. D.1). This influx of material is known to potentially induce numerous space weather issues on Earth. The efficiency of dayside reconnection, therefore, plays a pivotal role in determining the extent to which input from interplanetary space integrates with the magnetosphere. As a result, accurately predicting and mitigating space weather necessitates a comprehensive understanding of reconnection dynamics at the dayside magnetopause.

The low latitude boundary layer: The low latitude boundary layer (LLBL) exists as an extremely narrow region situated just inside the magnetopause, often spanning half the thickness of the magnetopause ($0.5R_E$ thick). Within this zone, plasma flow mirrors that of the magnetosheath, indicating that the magnetopause doesn't serve as an impermeable

barrier to plasma particles. Nonetheless, the precise mechanism and location where magnetosheath plasma crosses the magnetopause remain subjects of debate. Additionally, the LLBL is believed to extend into the dayside ionosphere. In cases of southward interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) conditions, the high latitude boundary layer (HLBL) or entry layer is situated poleward from the LLBL on the dayside.

The magnetosheath: Situated between the bow shock and the magnetopause, magnetosheath delineates the outermost boundary of the magnetosphere. Here, the plasma from the shocked solar wind flows around the magnetopause, exhibiting significantly higher density, temperature, and slower velocity compared to the ambient solar wind. Magnetic field lines become draped around the magnetopause, while the level of magnetic field turbulence markedly increases compared to the solar wind.

The polar cusps: The polar cusps, represent two distinctive high-altitude regions near the two magnetic poles where magnetosheath plasma gains direct entry to Earth. In this region the geomagnetic field lines guide the solar wind downward, intensifying its energy before it enters Earth's atmosphere (Holtet and Egeland, 1985; Russell, 2000, and references therein). This interaction results in the blending and collision of solar wind particles with those originating from Earth. The specific location of the cusps are contingent upon Earth's magnetic field dipole tilt and whether the magnetosphere reconnects with a southward or northward interplanetary magnetic field. Notably, during severe geomagnetic storm events, the cusp shifts toward lower latitudes, facilitating increased access of the solar wind to Earth's atmosphere.

The polar cap and auroral oval: The polar caps, characterized by areas of open field lines linking Earth's magnetic field to the IMF, serve as crucial interfaces between the ionosphere, magnetosphere, and solar wind (Burrell et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018). The polar caps exhibit intriguing physical processes: solar wind activity shifts the polar magnetic field lines from magnetic noon to magnetic midnight, where they eventually reconnect with geomagnetic field lines from the opposite hemisphere. Upon closure, these field lines migrate to lower magnetic latitudes before returning to the dayside due to Earth's rotation, forming the auroral oval. Within the auroral oval, where geomagnetic field lines are closed, they map to the plasma sheet and the plasma sheet boundary layer within the magnetosphere (see Fig. D.2).

At ionospheric altitudes, the open-closed field line boundary (OCB) or the polar cap boundary (PCB) delineates the boundary between the polar cap and the auroral oval, essentially separating the open and closed field lines. This boundary plays a pivotal role in determining the nature of coupling within the magnetosphere-ionosphere-thermosphere (MIT)

system, facilitated by field-aligned currents (FACs) (Milan et al., 2017). Consequently, it aids in understanding the strength of a geomagnetic storm.

Figure D.2 The illustration depicting the magnetospheric circulation during southward interplanetary magnetic field conditions. The diagram highlights critical aspects of the interaction between the solar wind and magnetosphere, such as the connection of magnetospheric field lines to the interplanetary field and their extension to the upper atmosphere. Sequential time points are marked by numbers. The driven circulation extends down to the polar ionosphere, as illustrated in the inset, revealing the dusk half of the double-celled ionosphere convection pattern. Auroras predominantly manifest in areas characterized by convection reversals. Image reproduced from: Luhmann and Solomon (2007).

The magnetotail: In contrast to the compressed and confined dayside magnetosphere, the nightside extends into a long “magnetotail” under the influence of the solar wind (Hones, 1986; Nishida et al., 1998). The magnetotail, stretched away from the sun by the solar wind, consists of two lobes: the northern and southern tail lobes. In the northern lobe, magnetic field lines point towards the north pole via the cusp, while in the southern lobe, they extend away from the southern polar region. These lobes are separated by a plasma sheet, characterized by a weaker magnetic field and a higher density of charged particles. Earth’s magnetotail extends beyond the orbit of the Moon and can span over $1000R_E$ in length (Fig. D.3). Magnetic field lines within Earth’s magnetotail can undergo reconnection (Petrukovich et al., 2016), leading to the acceleration of ions and electrons into the upper atmosphere of the polar cap region (Nagai et al., 2015). During periods of disturbed geomagnetic conditions, this phenomenon often results in active and expansive displays of the aurora.

Figure D.3 An open geomagnetosphere is depicted across both hemispheres of the sun, exhibiting varying magnetic polarity in the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF). Near Earth, three distinct types of magnetic field lines are evident: those originating from the interplanetary magnetic field, closed dipole field lines stemming from Earth, and hybrid lines that merge both, establishing a connection between Earth and the interplanetary medium. Additionally, dashed lines indicate neutral sheets where the interplanetary magnetic field diminishes. Image courtesy by: Anderson and Lin (1969); Kallenrode (2001).

The plasma sheet: The plasma sheet is a region of hot, dense plasma that stretches along the center of the magnetotail. Inside this region, the geomagnetic field lines are greatly stretched, and the plasma is both hot and dense. Adjacent to the plasma sheet lies the plasma sheet boundary layer, where the plasma is somewhat less dense and energetic. This boundary layer extends towards Earth deep into the ionosphere.

The plasma mantle: The plasma mantle is a region with open magnetic field lines. Originating from the magnetosheath, plasma infiltrates this region as the field lines are drawn downwards along the geomagnetic tail. While the density within the plasma mantle diminishes compared to that of the magnetosheath, the flow predominantly aligns parallel to the magnetosheath flow, albeit with a minor inward component directed towards the neutral sheet.

The ionosphere: The ionosphere is a layer in the thermospheric region of Earth's atmosphere where the abundance of charged particles – ions and electrons – affects radio wave propagation. These particles originate from extraterrestrial radiation, primarily from the

Sun, interacting with neutral atoms and molecules in the air. The ionosphere begins approximately 50 km above the Earth's surface, but becomes more prominent and influential above 80 km. Extending several hundred kilometers above the Earth's surface and spanning tens of thousands of kilometers into space, the upper regions of the ionosphere transition into the magnetosphere. Here, the behavior of charged particles is strongly influenced by Earth's and the Sun's magnetic fields. The lower part of the magnetosphere, overlapping with the ionosphere, hosts the spectacular aurora borealis and aurora australis displays. Additionally, within the magnetosphere lie the Van Allen radiation belts, where highly energized protons and electrons oscillate between Earth's magnetic poles.

Historically, the ionosphere was believed to consist of distinct layers labeled D, E, and F, with the F layer further divided into F1 and F2 regions. Although these layers are not precisely defined, the original nomenclature persists.³ **The D region**, situated at altitudes of about 70 to 90 km, is the lowest ionospheric region. Unlike the E and F regions, the D region experiences a significant reduction in free electrons during the night due to recombination with oxygen ions. Radio wave transmission is limited during the day, with reduced signal strength attributed to partial reflection from the D region. **The E region**, also known as the Kennelly-Heaviside layer, spans altitudes from 90 km to about 160 km. Ionization persists in the E region at night, albeit at a reduced level. This layer played a crucial role in Guglielmo Marconi's transatlantic radio communication in 1902. The E_s layer, characterized by sporadic patches of intense ionization, can reflect radio waves ranging from 50 MHz to occasionally 450 MHz, with events lasting minutes to hours. Extending from approximately 160 km upward, **the F region** possesses the highest concentration of free electrons. During the day, it is characterized by two distinct layers: the F1 layer and the more ionized F2 layer. At night, these layers merge around the level of the F2 layer, also known as the Appleton layer. The F region reflects radio waves up to about 35 megahertz, contingent on the peak electron concentration, typically around 10^6 electrons per cubic centimeter, but subject to variations influenced by the sunspot cycle. For more details about the ionosphere, refer to Hapgood (2022); Kamide and Chian (2007); Kivelson and Russell (1995) and references therein.

The IMF clock angle: The angle refers to the angle between the IMF and the terrestrial dayside magnetic field. When the angle is 0° , the two magnetic fields are aligned, while

³Edward V. Appleton, a pioneer in early radio exploration of the ionosphere, is credited with the development of this naming convention. Appleton initially utilized the symbol E to denote the electric field of the wave reflected from the primary ionospheric layer under study. Subsequently, upon discovering a secondary layer at a higher altitude, he introduced the symbol F for the corresponding reflected wave. Upon suspecting the existence of a layer at a lower altitude, he introduced the additional symbol D. Over time, these symbols became associated with the ionospheric layers themselves rather than solely with the reflected wave fields.

an angle of 180° indicates they are anti-aligned, corresponding to a mostly southward IMF (Fadiyah and Herdiwijaya, 2022).

D.2 Magnetospheric current systems

Figure D.4 Panel A of the figure illustrates the magnetosphere and highlights various current regions. Moving to Panel B, it presents the Chapman-Ferraro dayside magnetopause currents, represented as a green-shaded surface on a simplified wire diagram of the magnetopause. The Earth is depicted as a small sphere at the axis origin, while the Sun is positioned at the lower left. Panel C depicts the closure of tail currents through return current on the magnetopause, shown in light blue on the wire diagram of the magnetopause. In Panel D, Region 1 field-aligned currents are illustrated as red bands, accompanied by two possible closure paths: one directly to the magnetopause and the other via the far tail plasma sheet. Panel E zooms in closer to the Earth to showcase the symmetric ring current (eastward and westward, depicted in brown and blue, respectively), as well as the cut ring currents on the dayside (in yellow). Lastly, Panel F shifts the perspective to the evening sector, displaying Region 2 field-aligned currents and partial ring current in purple, alongside the banana current represented in orange. It's important to note that the image is adapted from the works cited (Ganushkina et al. (2018); Kivelson and Russell (1995)).

In everyday context, the term “current” typically evokes the image of electric current, where charged particles, predominantly electrons, flow along a wire and provide power to keep the household appliances running.⁴ While household currents sustain our daily lives,

⁴The concept of current extends beyond electricity and extensively describes fluid flow, a phenomenon prevalent in various natural processes observed in space science and geo-science. Other than the magneto-

other manifestations of currents exist beyond the confines of our homes and permeate near-Earth space.

Chapman-Ferraro magnetopause current

The magnetopause current, also known as the Chapman-Ferraro current, constitutes a significant current system flowing along the magnetopause boundary. This current system plays a crucial role in generating a magnetic field that effectively shields the terrestrial dipole field from penetration by the solar wind. The mechanism behind the formation of the magnetopause current lies in the trajectories of magnetosheath protons and electrons interacting with the geomagnetic field. As magnetosheath particles encounter regions of increased magnetic field strength, they are compelled to return to the magnetosheath after completing only half of their gyration (Fig. D.5). Since protons and electrons gyrate in opposite directions around the magnetospheric field, their motion within the boundary results in generation of a current. In regions where the magnetic field is predominantly northward within the boundary, the current flows from dawn to dusk across the equatorial magnetopause and from dusk to dawn across the high-latitude magnetopause tailward of the cusp openings (refer to Fig. D.4).

While this simple scenario predicts the magnetopause current sheet to have a thickness on the order of one ion gyroradius, observations from spacecraft such as the International Sun-Earth Explorer (ISEE) and Cluster satellites have shown it to be approximately 5–10 ion gyroradii, equivalent to several hundred kilometers (Haaland et al., 2004; Le and Russell, 1994). This increased thickness is attributed to the effects of kinetic instabilities that smear out the thin current sheet.

When studying the dynamic properties of ionized gases with low density, Parker (1957) demonstrated that under static conditions, the perpendicular current density \mathbf{J}_\perp to the magnetic field \mathbf{B} can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{J}_\perp = \frac{\mathbf{B}}{B^2} \times \left[\nabla p_\perp + (p_\parallel - p_\perp) \frac{(\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{B}}{B^2} \right],$$

where p_\parallel and p_\perp represent plasma pressure parallel and perpendicular to the magnetic field, respectively. This equation holds true in the presence of quasi-static equilibrium or

spheric currents – which is a plasma-based electric current ultimately – one example of fluid current occurs deep within the Earth’s mantle, where molten rock undergoes slow, millennia-long motions, completing loops over vast timescales. Similarly, the ocean currents, circulating around the globe, undergo centuries-long journeys, traversing various depths and experiencing changes in temperature and salinity along their paths. Groundwater flow through fractures in rocks presents another instance, meandering through surface water reservoirs and even the atmosphere before completing its loop in the hydrological cycle. Air currents, such as the jet stream and trade winds, represent segments of the large-scale atmospheric circulation system.

Figure D.5 Schematic diagram depicting the deflection of solar wind electrons and protons at the magnetopause boundary, leading to the finite thickness of the magnetopause and the presence of the Chapman-Ferraro current. Image reproduced from Kallenrode (2001); Kivelson and Russell (1995); Willis (1971).

force-balanced state. For isotropic pressure p , neglecting the inertial terms, the equation simplifies to:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\perp} = \frac{\mathbf{B} \times \nabla p}{B^2}.$$

In the simplest model of the magnetopause current system, the magnetic field outside the magnetopause and the contribution of particles within it are disregarded. Essentially, the magnetopause current system acts as a boundary, separating the shocked magnetosheath plasma from the “empty” magnetic dipole field inside. In this scenario, the magnetopause current density can be written in the form:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{MP}} = \frac{\mathbf{B}_{\text{dp}}}{B_{\text{dp}}^2} \times \nabla (\rho_m u^2 + p),$$

where B_{dp} represents the magnetospheric field at the magnetopause. At the magnetopause boundary, the total pressure in the magnetosheath is approximately equal to the free-streaming solar wind kinetic pressure. Therefore, an estimate of the magnetopause current magnitude can be expressed as:

$$j_{MP} \approx \frac{1}{B_{dp}} \frac{\rho_{SW} v_{SW}^2}{\Delta},$$

where Δ denotes the thickness of the magnetopause. This analytical insight reveals that the magnetopause currents form closed loops across the dayside portion of the magnetosphere, with an average current density of 20 nA/m². Similarly, for a pressure of 2 nPa on the magnetosheath side of the magnetopause, which closely aligns with the solar wind dynamic pressure, and a magnetic field strength of 60 nT within the magnetopause layer, the surface current density is calculated to be 0.03 A/m.

The magnetotail current

In the magnetotail, a distinctive feature is the presence of a thin sheet of current that flows nearly parallel to the equatorial plane throughout the magnetotail and divides the tail-region into two halves with nearly uniform magnetic fields of opposite directions. Specifically, the current flows from the East terminator (Dawn-side) to the West terminator (Dusk-side) of the sheet. Upon reaching the magnetopause at the west terminator, the magnetotail current must find closure, and Axford et al. (1965) identified that it closes via the magnetopause above and below the relatively strong magnetic field regions of the tail, forming a system resembling the Greek letter θ , referred to as a ‘return current.’ Figure D.4 illustrates the schematic view of the tail current with closure via the return current on the magnetopause.

As the geomagnetic tail originates from highly stretched (“open”) magnetic field lines extending from the polar cap, the magnetic flux leaving the polar cap can be calculated as the radial component of the magnetic field integrated over the polar cap area:

$$\Phi_{PC} = 2\pi (R_E \cos(\theta_{PC}))^2 B_{dip},$$

where B_{dip} is equatorial magnetic field strength of Earth’s dipole, θ_{PC} represents the magnetic latitude of the equatorward edge of the polar cap, and $R_E \cos(\theta_{PC})$ denotes the effective radius of the polar cap region. This flux is then transported outward into the magnetotail. Assuming the lobe to be semicircular with a radius of R_{tail} and a magnetic field strength of B_{tail} , the flux within one lobe is given by $\Phi_{PC} = \pi R_{tail} B_{tail} / 2$.

Equating these fluxes yields:

$$R_{tail} = \sqrt{\frac{4 B_{dip}}{B_{tail}}} \cos(\theta_{PC}) R_E$$

For $\theta_{PC} = 75^\circ$ and $B_{tail} = 20$ nT, the radius of the magnetotail is calculated to be $20R_E$. Given typical plasma sheet parameters such as number density $n \sim 0.3$ cm⁻³, ion temperature $T_i \sim 4.2$ keV, and electron temperature $T_e \sim 0.6$ keV, along with this magnetic strength and radius of the tail, the current density is estimated to be 30 mA/m or 30 A/km or 2×10^5 A/ R_E . It means that 10^6 A is carried in each of the $5R_E$ of the tail, potentially having significant impacts on the ionosphere during storm times.

A highly debated issue regarding this current system revolves around its proximity to Earth's nightside while meeting the closure criteria according to conventional standards. In their study, Ganushkina et al. (2015) examined the established definitions of the cross-tail current. Essentially, the tail current is typically described as a westward equatorial current occurring on the nightside beyond $6.6 R_E$, connecting to the magnetopause. This current flows within regions characterized by stretched magnetic field lines and uniform plasma pressure, carried by particles with energies less than 20 keV.

It's worth noting that while the tail current remains a consistent and steady system when viewed on a broad scale across the magnetosphere, it comprises numerous highly dynamic currents on a smaller scale. These include depolarisation front currents, as demonstrated by (Liu et al., 2013), and small-scale field-aligned currents, as evidenced by studies conducted by Nakamura et al. (2001); Sergeev et al. (1996); Takada et al. (2008).

The ring current

Early studies in magnetospheric physics introduced a current flowing around the Earth in the clockwise direction with the shape of a ring or, rather, a toroid (Schmidt, 1921; Störmer, 1912). The concept of this ring current played a significant role in the initial understanding of geomagnetic storms (Chapman and Ferraro, 1931, 1941). The current flowing around the Earth in the clockwise direction will depress the magnetic field at the Earth's surface, since the direction of its magnetic field is opposite to the Earth's internal magnetic field. The measured disturbances of the ground magnetic field during geomagnetic storms were attributed to the ring current increase and decrease Akasofu and Chapman (1961); Kamide (1974); Kamide and Fukushima (1971).

The early measurements of the ring current particles were made onboard the Orbiting Geophysical Observatory 3 (Frank, 1967) and Explorer 45 (Smith and Hoffman, 1974) satellites. The first complete observational evidences of the ring current composition and structure came from the Active Magnetospheric Particle Tracer Explorers/Charge Composition Explorer satellite which was in elliptical orbit with 9 R_E apogee. The obtained radial plasma pressure profiles in the magnetosphere contained pressure increasing earthward with a peak around 3 R_E and then decreasing toward the Earth (De Michelis et al., 1997; Lui and Hamil-

ton, 1992; Lui et al., 1987; Spence et al., 1989). This feature is consistent with the two ring currents, one flowing around the Earth clockwise (westward) outside of the pressure peak and the other anticlockwise (eastward) inside of the pressure peak. Figure D.4 presents the schematic view of the symmetric ring current. The light brown current near the Earth flows eastward, and the light blue current flows westward. The derived current densities for the eastward ring current were typically about 2 nA/m^2 , whereas westward ring current can be of $\sim 1\text{--}4 \text{ nA/m}^2$ during quiet times and of $\sim 7 \text{ nA/m}^2$ during storm times but can be also as large as 50 nA/m^2 (Vallat et al., 2005).

The large-scale structure of the ring current was later confirmed by numerous studies. They include, for example, the analysis of the magnetic field data from the ISEE, Active Magnetospheric Particle Tracer Explorers/Charge Composition Explorer and Polar missions, the Combined Release and Radiation Effects Satellite, the remote sensing of energetic neutral atoms (ENAs) emitted from the ring current from ISEE-1 spacecraft and the Van Allen Probes mission (Buzulukova et al., 2010; C:son Brandt et al., 2002; Gkioulidou et al., 2016; Goldstein et al., 2012; Jorgensen et al., 2004; Kistler et al., 2016; Le et al., 2004; Menz et al., 2017; Pollock et al., 2001; Zhao et al., 2016, 2015).

The traditional toroidal shape of the ring current has been questioned based on the fact that on the dayside there are two magnetic field minima above and below the equatorial plane. On the nightside, the magnetic field lines have only one minimum. This structure of the magnetic field determines the drift trajectories of particles. The ring current does not go around the Earth as one system but splits into two branches in the dayside magnetosphere and forms the high-latitude continuation of the ordinary ring current (Antonova, 2003, 2004; Antonova and Ganushkina, 2000). This current was named the cut-ring current (CRC). Figure D.4 presents the schematic view of the cut ring current shown by the yellow ribbon. The initial verification of the existence of such a current was done by analyzing the radial profiles of plasma pressure gradients obtained from the THEMIS-B satellite data (Antonova et al., 2009) but an extensive analysis of the global plasma pressure distribution is still required.

The ring current system containing eastward and westward currents has been considered symmetric but from the observational point of view, the ring current is never purely symmetric (Jorgensen et al., 2004; Le et al., 2004). This system is symmetric in a sense that all the current goes around the Earth, and it is a closed system but it is almost always asymmetric in terms of the current density. The current density is not the same at the different locations around the Earth. It can be more symmetric during quiet times but during storm times it is asymmetric, especially during the storm peak (Liemohn et al., 2001). The symmetry can be restored during storm recovery phase though not always fully (Daglis, 2006; Ebihara and Ejiri, 2003; Ganushkina et al., 2018; Ganushkina et al., 2015; Jordanova et al.,

2020; Kozyra and Liemohn, 2003). The magnetosphere itself is asymmetric due to solar wind-magnetosphere interactions resulting in the compression of the magnetic field lines on the dayside and stretching on the nightside (Fig. D.6). During disturbed times, more plasma is injected and transported from the nightside plasma sheet to the inner magnetosphere. Due to this process, the plasma pressure distribution in the inner magnetosphere becomes highly asymmetric with a gradient in the azimuthal direction which is reflected in the spatial asymmetry of the ring current. The concept of the partial ring current and its closure to the ionosphere was suggested by Alfvén in 1950s (Egeland and Burke, 2012). In situ satellite observations showed a fairly symmetric ring current during geomagnetically quiet conditions and an asymmetric current distribution during storm times, symmetrizing again during the storm recovery phase (De Michelis et al., 1999; Ebihara and Ejiri, 2003; Korth et al., 2000; Le et al., 2004; Lui, 2003). The westward ring current that the partial ring current is a part of can be as intense as 50 nA/m^2 in current density. Another partial ring current, known as the banana current, arises from asymmetrical plasma pressure distributions with localized peaks and unbalanced magnetization. This current flows around these peaks, contributing to the asymmetric eastward current. During geomagnetic storms, it can reach 4–5 R_E and several MA, but diminishes to $<0.1 \text{ MA}$ during quiet periods.

One more current system is shown in orange in Fig D.4F and it is the so-called banana current. If the plasma pressure distribution is not symmetric and has a peak localized both radially and azimuthally, a magnetization current will flow around this. The banana current is the part of the current that flows around the localized pressure peak and accounts for all of the asymmetric eastward current. The banana current can flow at 4-5 R_E and be of several MA during storm times but its intensity can drop to small numbers ($<0.1 \text{ MA}$) during extended quiet periods. Due to the decrease of the magnetic field with radial distance, the outer westward current is always larger than the eastward current, and this unbalanced magnetization current closes through the ionosphere as the partial ring current (Ganushkina et al., 2018, and references therein).

For a mathematical examination of the ring current, the fundamental physics lies in the gradient-curvature drift, which operates in opposite directions for electrons and ions, resulting in a net current. Assuming all ring current particles are equatorially trapped on an “average” field line characterized by a length scale L such that their equatorial pitch angle is 90° , the gradient-curvature drift becomes:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{GC}} = -\frac{3}{2} \frac{mv^2}{q} \frac{L^2}{B_E R_E} \mathbf{e}_\phi$$

Here, all particles are located at the equator at a planetocentric distance of LR_E . The total current, I_ϕ , can be expressed as:

Figure D.6 Panel A depicts the trajectory of a mirroring particle within the magnetosphere. Panel B showcases drift paths for ring current and partial ring current ions in the equatorial plane. Panel C demonstrates the combined motions of trapped particles in a dipole magnetic field. Image courtesy of: Gombosi (1998); Jordanova et al. (2020)

$$I_{\phi} = -3 \frac{L^2}{B_E R_E} \sum_{\substack{\text{electrons} \\ \text{and ions}}} N_t \frac{m_t v_t^2}{2}$$

However, we aim to express the total current carried by the ring current in terms of the total energy of ring current particles, E_{RC} . In this approximation:

$$E_{RC} = 2\pi L R_E \sum_{\substack{\text{electrons} \\ \text{and ions}}} N_t \frac{m_t v_t^2}{2}$$

Thus, the toroidal current becomes:

$$I_\phi = -\frac{3LR_{RC}}{2\pi B_E R_E^2}$$

The magnetic field at the center of a circular loop of radius r is given by the Biot-Savart equation: $\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2r} \mathbf{e}_z$. In the case of the ring current, the magnetic field perturbation created by the ring current at the center of the Earth can be expressed as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{B} = -\frac{3\mu_0 E_{RC}}{4\pi B_E R_E^3} \mathbf{e}_z$$

where \mathbf{e}_z is pointing along the magnetic axis. Importantly, the magnetic field perturbation is independent of L . The negative sign indicates that the ring current weakens the geomagnetic field.

However, the drift path of a ring current particle is not necessarily a closed orbit due to equatorial electric fields in the magnetosphere, typically pointing from dawn to dusk. The $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ guiding center drift in the equatorial plane can be expressed as:

$$v_E = \left| \frac{\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{E}}{B_{\text{Dipole}}^2} \right|_{\text{eq}} = \frac{E}{B_{\text{Dipole}}} = L^3 \frac{E}{B_E}$$

where the subscript eq refers to the equatorial plane, B_{Dipole} is the dipole field, and B_E is the magnetic field strength at the terrestrial equator. In this scenario, the electric field vector is directed from dawn to dusk. For equatorially bouncing electrons and ions, this electric drift is sunward, and it is proportional to L^3 (Fig. D.6). However, as the gradient-curvature drift for these particles is proportional to L^2 , at larger geocentric distances the electric drift typically dominates over the magnetic gradient-curvature drift. Close to Earth, the magnetic drift dominates, resulting in closed trajectories, which define the region of the ring current. Further out in the inner magnetosphere, the sunward drifting particles, due to the magnetospheric electric field, are deflected around the Earth by the magnetic drift, forming the partial ring current.

A fraction of the ring current is composed of relativistic electrons and very energetic (MeV) ions too. While these particles contribute relatively little to the ring current, they are crucial for safety considerations due to their ability to penetrate deep into dense materials, potentially causing radiation damage to spacecraft systems or humans.

The field align current and Pedersen current

In 1908, Kristian Birkeland of Norway inferred from his examination of auroral phenomena that auroral zone current systems are closed by vertical electrical currents that extend beyond

the ionosphere (Birkeland, 1908). However, this concept faced rejection by Sydney Chapman, a prominent authority in space science during the 1930s. Consequently, Birkeland's proposition did not gain credibility until the late 1960s, when a convergence of satellite and ground-based observations provided compelling evidence supporting the existence of field-aligned currents and presently, these currents are termed Birkeland currents. For instances, the magnetometer onboard the low-altitude polar orbiting Triad Satellite provided three components of the magnetic field in the northern polar regions: firstly, a radially downward component nearly parallel to the main geomagnetic field, then a transverse component to the main geomagnetic field in the east-west magnetic direction, and lastly, a transverse component to the main geomagnetic field in the north-south magnetic direction (Ganushkina et al., 2018, and references therein).

Figure D.7 (Left) Schematic illustrating the main large-scale current systems linked to the polar region of Earth. (Right) Representation of magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling through field-aligned Region 1 and 2 currents, as well as Pedersen and Hall currents in the ionosphere. Figures reproduced from: Kivelson and Russell (1995)

Iijima and Potemra (1976) categorized the field-aligned currents into Region 1 and Region 2 currents. Region 1 currents, which flow outward from the ionosphere, represent the poleward currents, while Region 2 currents, which flow into the ionosphere, represent the equatorward currents. The other end of the Region 1 currents is located on closed field lines and is connected to the plasma sheet, boundary layer, and the nightside magnetopause (Fig. D.7). Also, with rising geomagnetic activity, the Region 1 current system expands, displacing the Chapman-Ferraro current system (Ganushkina et al., 2018, and references therein). The specific physical mechanisms responsible for the formation of this nightside segment of Region 1 field-aligned currents remain uncertain. Potential contributing factors include processes occurring in the boundary layer and in the plasma sheet. At distances where partial ring current flows, the azimuthal plasma pressure gradients are directed earthward and

slightly toward midnight, corresponding to the generation of Region 2 field-aligned currents (Fig. D.7) (Ganushkina et al., 2018, and references therein). Pedersen currents traverse between the Region 1 and Region 2 Birkeland current sheets, completing the circuit of charge flow through the ionosphere (Fig. D.7). Notably, at any given local time, one region involves current entering the ionosphere along geomagnetic field lines, while the other region involves current leaving the ionosphere. Additionally, there exists a Pedersen current that traverses across the pole from the dawn side to the dusk side of the Region 1 current sheet. Ultimately, it is the Pedersen and Hall conductivities – as they are contingent on plasma density, which, in turn, is influenced by auroral or solar ionization – that lead to Joule heating of the ionosphere. This serves as a significant source of energy dissipation from the magnetosphere to the atmosphere, particularly during solar storms.

D.3 Storm impacts on geo-magnetosphere and geomagnetic indices

Indices are extensively utilized across various domains to track the development of diverse phenomena, furnishing pertinent, reliable, and condensed information. Whether pertaining to geomagnetic activity, stock market trends, geopolitical issues, or human well-being, an index serves as a numerical representation of an event or series of events. Each individual index value aims to describe the phenomenon under scrutiny within a fixed time interval, neither substituting the original data nor interpreting them. It is imperative that the relationship between an index value and the original data be clearly defined, kept as simple as possible, and that the regularity and homogeneity of the index data series be carefully maintained.

The earliest attempts to characterize geomagnetic activity date back to the late 1800s, focusing on estimating daily geomagnetic disturbances. During this period, the daily range, computed as the difference between the highest and lowest values recorded on selected geomagnetic components at observatories in Greenwich, London, and Colaba, India, was utilized. The introduction of the “C” character, describing the relative degree of disturbance of magnetograms, led to the calculation of the international character C_i , spanning the years 1884–1975. However, the inherent limitations of the C_i index necessitated the development of new indices enabling objective monitoring of irregular variations. The K index, pioneered by Bartels et al. (1939), served as a crucial advancement, subsequently leading to the computation of “Kp” indices. Despite its significance, the Kp index remained somewhat imperfect due to limited data availability, particularly during the Cold War era and prior to the International Geophysical Year.

Figure D.8 The worldwide distribution of operational geomagnetic observatories starting from 2010, displayed using a Mollweide projection. Information about the observatories, including their names, IAGA codes, latitude, longitude, elevation, and operational years, can be accessed at the IAGA official website.

Following the International Geophysical Year, advancements in magnetospheric physics and improvements in the observatory network facilitated the design of new indices for refined geomagnetic activity description. Figure D.8 depicts the global network of active geomagnetic observatories as it existed beginning in 2010. The introduction of indices such as “Dst,” “AE,” and “am” provided more comprehensive insights. Additionally, lists of magnetic events compiled in the early 20th century were streamlined, with only “ssc” and “sfe” lists remaining compiled as per an IAGA resolution passed in 1975. Subsequently, indices leveraging high-quality digital data emerged, including “SYM” and “ASY” indices, “IHV” and “IDV” indices, “ αm ” and “ αa ” indices, and indices based on geomagnetic pulsations (Mandea and Korte, 2011; Mayaud, 1980, and references therein).

Eventually, a specific index serves two distinct groups: primarily, those who directly analyze the phenomenon itself, and those who utilize it as a benchmark while studying related phenomena. It’s evident that certain potential errors associated with the use of geomagnetic indices always pertain to the user. For example, the Kp index, with its fixed time interval of 3 hours, though it can give a quick brief idea about the strength of an event, cannot pinpoint the exact onset time of a geomagnetic activity. So it is upon the user, who chooses an index for the study based on the need of their situation.

Disturbance Storm Time index

The Dst index at a time t , $Dst(t)$, is defined as the average of the disturbance variation of the H component, $D_i(t)$, at the four observatories ($i = 1 - 4$) divided by the average of the cosines of the dipole latitudes at the observatories for normalization to the dipole equator:

$$Dst(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 D_i(t)}{\sum_{i=1}^4 \cos(\lambda_i)}$$

where λ_i is the magnetic dipole latitude of the i -th observatory. Note that the normalization is by the average of the four cosines and NOT for each $D_i(t)$ by $\cos(\lambda_i)$. According to Sugiura et al. (1991), this normalization procedure has been found to minimize undesired effects from missing hourly values.

Each $D_i(t)$ is calculated from the observed $H(t)$ by subtracting the baseline value of the geomagnetic main field, $H_{base}(t)$, and Sq (solar quiet) variation, $Sq(t)$. The baseline value is defined for each observatory in a manner that takes into account the secular variation of the annual mean values of H , calculated from the internationally selected five quietest days. The baseline is expressed by a power series in time and the coefficients for terms up to the quadratic are determined by the method of least squares fitting, using the annual means for the current year and the four preceding years:

$$H_{base}(\tau) = A + B\tau + C\tau^2$$

where τ is time in years measured from a reference epoch.

The solar quiet daily variation, Sq , is derived for each observatory as follows. The average Sq variation for each month is determined from the values of $H(t)$ for the five Q-days of the month. These quietest days are determined in UT. In order to define an average Sq variation of each observatory, the five local days that have the maximum overlap with the five Q-days are used. Using hourly values immediately before and immediately after the local days thus selected, the linear change is subtracted from the Sq variation, and they are averaged at each local time.

The 12 sets of the monthly average Sq , determined for the year, are expanded in a double Fourier series with local time, T , and month number, M , as two variables:

$$Sq(T, M) = \sum_j \sum_k A_{jk} \cos(jT + \alpha_j) \cos(kM + \beta_k)$$

From this representation, $Sq(t)$ are calculated at any UT hour, t , of the year for each observatory. The $H_{base}(t)$ and $Sq(t)$ determined in this way are subtracted from the observed $H(t)$ to obtain the disturbance variation $D_i(t)$ for each observatory.

Magnetic disturbances in middle and low latitudes during a storm result from various currents within the magnetosphere, ionosphere, and induced currents within the Earth. It's widely believed that the axially symmetric part, as indicated by the Dst index, primarily originates from the ring current. Additionally, the neutral sheet current flowing across the magnetospheric tail also contributes to field decreases near the Earth. The compression of the magnetosphere due to solar wind pressure further adds to the symmetric variation, which manifests as a positive variation in the Dst index. Furthermore, a current induced within the Earth by magnetic field variations of magnetospheric and/or ionospheric origin contributes to the associated induced magnetic field, reported to be approximately 20–30% of the Dst index, depending on the phase of magnetic storms. Effects from field-aligned currents might also persist due to insufficient cancellation in the averaging process of the four observatory data. However, these effects are expected to diminish when conducting statistical analysis over a sufficiently long time series of the Dst index.

The reference level for Dst is typically set such that on the five quietest days (Q-days), the average Dst index is zero. Nonetheless, even during these quietest days, a southward-directed magnetic field produced by the equatorial current system in the magnetosphere, often referred to as the quiet time ring current, may exist. Its magnitude has been estimated by various satellite observations. For instance, estimates range from -25 nT to -13 nT. Although these values seem reasonable, there's considerable difference among them, thus necessitating further study to determine the absolute reference level for the Dst variation, which may vary with the solar cycle.

The Dst index is frequently utilized to estimate the baseline value with 1 nT accuracy during geomagnetic absolute measurements. However, caution is necessary regarding the accuracy of the baseline value, i.e., $Dst = 0$ nT. Several uncertainties exist in the baseline determination, such as the “quiet time ring current” and the “day-to-day” variability of the Sq field. For Quick Look Dst (QL-Dst) and provisional Dst, the absolute value of the H provided from each observatory is tentative, often differing by more than 10 nT among QL-Dst, provisional Dst, and final Dst. Hence, the absolute accuracy generally does not exceed 10 nT for QL-Dst and provisional Dst, and 5 nT for (final) Dst. These accuracy values themselves require further investigation (Mandea and Korte, 2011).

SYM-H and associated indices

To characterize the asymmetric and symmetric disturbance fields in mid-latitudes with high temporal resolution (i.e., 1 minute), longitudinally asymmetric (ASY) and symmetric (SYM) disturbance indices were introduced and derived for both the horizontal (H) and orthogonal (East-West) components (D). For the horizontal direction H (pointing positive towards the geomagnetic dipole pole in the Northern hemisphere), ASY-H and SYM-H indices were formulated, while for the orthogonal direction D, ASY-D and SYM-D were defined. SYM-H represents the symmetric disturbance field, akin to the hourly Dst index but computed using 1-minute values from 6 different station sets and a slightly modified coordinate system. Although in reality, there are 11 observatories, and their data can be swapped depending on availability. Similarly, ASY-H closely resembles the asymmetric indices proposed by various researchers (Iyemori, 1990; Iyemori and Rao, 1996; Iyemori et al., 2009).⁵

The primary distinction between SYM-H and the hourly Dst index lies in their time resolution. SYM-H provides more detailed insights into rapid variations of solar wind parameters, such as dynamic pressure and the southward component of the interplanetary magnetic field, as well as the impact of substorm onset, compared to the hourly Dst index (Mandea and Korte, 2011).

Storm Sudden Commencements

Storm Sudden Commencements (SSCs) denote a sudden increase or decrease in the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field, signifying the onset of a geomagnetic storm or heightened activity lasting at least an hour.

In the definition proposed by Mayaud (1973), two key factors determine SSCs: the abruptness of the event's commencement and the change in magnetic activity rhythm before and after the sudden occurrence. The latter implies that while some SSCs are included in the list, they may not necessarily be followed by an actual magnetic storm.

This definition underwent modification during the 2009 IAGA Assembly in Sopron (Hungary) to incorporate advancements in understanding rapid variations and facilitate computer based detection:

- A threshold for the rate of change in dX/dt was introduced.
- A quantitative criterion, utilizing am and Dst indices, was adopted to differentiate between SSCs followed by a storm and those categorized as sudden impulses (SI) if no storm ensues.

⁵ASY and SYM indices are routinely generated by WDC-C2 in Kyoto, Japan, and are accessible online through their Internet platform.

- A quantitative criterion, utilizing am and Dst indices, was adopted to differentiate between SSCs followed by a storm and those categorized as sudden impulses (SI) if no storm ensues.

The K and AE index

The K index, introduced by Bartels et al. (1939), serves to objectively monitor geomagnetic activity, particularly the irregular component known as “particle variations.” Bartels distinguished between geomagnetic changes stemming from solar “wave radiations” and those from “particle radiations,” postulating the existence of “M regions” emitting particle radiation without visible solar spots, later linked to coronal holes. It became a standard tool for monitoring magnetic activity. The K index, particularly Kp, endorsed by IAGA, relies on irregular variations in horizontal geomagnetic components, with a 3-hour derivation interval based on 11 northern and 2 southern observatories, stationed between 44° and 60° northern or southern geomagnetic latitude. Despite subjective elements in determining “Smoothed Range” (SR), trained observers generally concur on K index magnitudes. Bartels et al. (1939) established ten ranges at Niemegk observatory, with individual indices ranging from 0 to 9, representing the largest disturbances during a 3-hour UT interval.

The Auroral-electrojet (AE) index, proposed by Davis and Sugiura (1966), quantifies global electrojet activity within the auroral zone. Initially computed at NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center, its calculation shifted to the Geophysical Institute of the University of Alaska, then to the World Data Center A for Solar-Terrestrial Physics (WDC-A for STP) in Boulder, Colorado. WDC-C2 later took over production, consistently publishing 1.0-minute values since the International Magnetospheric Study period. Derived from geomagnetic variations observed at 12 selected auroral zone observatories, AE index normalizes data by averaging monthly values on quietest days. It then calculates upper (AU) and lower (AL) envelopes from deviations, defining AE index as their difference. AU and AL represent eastward and westward auroral electrojet intensities, respectively, while AE index signifies overall electrojet activity, and AO index measures equivalent zonal current. The term “AE indices” encompasses AU, AL, AE, and AO, with stations noted for closures and replacements over time.

Appendix E

The physics behind magnetic reconnection

Magnetic reconnection serves as a fundamental process shaping the dynamics of magnetic fields and the conversion of magnetic energy into kinetic energy within cosmic plasmas. Originally proposed by Giovanelli (1946), the concept gained traction in the 1950s among solar physicists striving to elucidate phenomena like solar flares, which demand immense energy supplies, on the order of $10^{27} - 10^{28}$ ergs per second, in the lower layers of the solar atmosphere (Parker, 1957; Sweet, 1958). These events necessitate a pre-existing reservoir of energy, typically stored in the form of magnetic energy, as solar flares are short-lived, lasting only about 30 minutes, requiring a rapid release of stored energy.

James Dungey, in his 1950 PhD thesis, first introduced the term “magnetic reconnection” while presenting an “open magnetosphere” model for Earth. Dungey’s groundbreaking work outlined how solar wind’s mass, energy, and momentum interact with Earth’s magnetosphere. His concept was further expounded upon in a seminal paper published in 1961 (Dungey, 1961). Dungey envisioned magnetic field lines and plasma converging toward a magnetic neutral point or line, where they undergo cutting and subsequent reconnection with altered configurations, leading to an outflow away from the neutral point or line. This cutting and reconnecting of magnetic field lines suggest the presence of dissipative effects at the site of reconnection.

In ideal systems devoid of dissipative effects, reconnection is inhibited. However, in resistive systems, such as those involving collisions between electrons and ions, resistivity enables the necessary irreversible dissipation for field line cutting. Even in collisionless systems, some dissipative effect allows for the generation of electric fields conducive to reconnection. Thus, magnetic reconnection marks a deviation from ideal magnetohydrodynam-

ics (MHD) and Alfvén’s theorem, particularly in large-scale regions of highly-conducting plasma.

In light of this, William Ian Axford, a prominent space and magnetospheric scientist from New Zealand, summarized his perspective during the Workshop on “Magnetic Reconnection in Space and Laboratory Plasmas” in October 1983. His summary, known as the “Axford conjecture,” emphasizes that magnetic reconnection necessitates a non-zero electrical resistivity or departure from ideal MHD. However, it underscores that the large-scale properties of the process are predominantly governed by global dynamics and boundary conditions rather than specific values of resistivity or other non-MHD effects (Axford, 1984).

Magnetic diffusion

Magnetic reconnection is believed to occur within a “diffusion” region where phenomena beyond Alfvén’s ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) facilitate a sharp yet gradual transition between asymptotically sheared magnetic fields. This transition enables the interconnection of previously unlinked, yet sheared, magnetic field lines, resulting in a reorganization of their topology.

Theoretically, The motion of the bulk plasma population and the time evolution of magnetic field lines are coupled by the induction equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta_m \nabla^2 \mathbf{B}$$

Here, η_m represents the viscosity of the magnetic field commonly known as the magnetic diffusivity, given by $\eta_m = \frac{1}{\sigma_0 \mu_0}$, where σ_0 is the conductivity and μ_0 is the permeability of free space. It’s important to note that σ_0 is not necessarily the collisional conductivity but can also be influenced by complex plasma processes leading to anomalous (collisionless) conductivity (Gombosi, 1998, Chapter 14).

In nearly stagnating one-dimensional plasmas, the convective term $\nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$ can be neglected, and the time evolution of the magnetic field \mathbf{B} entirely relies on magnetic diffusion:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \eta \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{B}}{\partial x^2}.$$

For simplicity, let’s denote η_m as η . So, as time progresses, the initial magnetic field “diffuses” away with a characteristic time-scale $\tau_d = \frac{L_D^2}{\eta}$, where L_D is the characteristic length scale. Consequently, for very small values of magnetic diffusivity, this characteristic time-scale can become very large. In the extreme scenario where η tends to 0, the diffusion time becomes infinite, and the magnetic field becomes “frozen” into the plasma.

Figure E.1 Panel **A** depicts a schematic representation of magnetic field reconnection. Panel **B** shows the time evolution of merging magnetic field lines. Distance and time are normalized to x/x_0 and $\eta t/x_0^2$, respectively, where x_0 represents an arbitrary length. The curves shown correspond to $t = \eta t/x_0^2$ values of 0, 0.1, and 1, respectively. Image reproduced from Gombosi (1998).

During a magnetic reconnection event, when two slowly moving slabs of plasma meet, they create a nearly stagnating plasma topology with a discontinuous magnetic field at the interface ($x = 0$) as shown in Fig. E.1. Assuming the antiparallel magnetic fields in the two slabs are $\pm B_0$ in the z direction, the initial condition is a discontinuous jump from $B_z = B_0$ to $B_z = -B_0$, such that L_D becomes zero. In this scenario, the solution of the 1D diffusion becomes:

$$B_z(x, t) = -B_0 \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{\eta t}}\right)$$

At $t = 0$, this describes the discontinuous solution, while at later times, the discontinuity “erodes.” This erosion can be observed in Fig. E.1, which illustrates the variation of the z component of the magnetic field. As time progresses, the magnetic field “dissipates” near the tangential discontinuity, and the thickness of the transition region or the current sheet region increases with time as $\sqrt{4\eta t}$ (Gombosi, 1998, Chapter 14). In such a scenario, even though magnetic flux remains conserved, the magnetic energy density $B^2/2\mu_0$ decreases with time, and the magnetic energy is ohmically converted into heat:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} \right) = -\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{J}$$

Here, the electric field \mathbf{E} is nonzero in the current layer separating the two plasma slabs, and \mathbf{J} is the current density.

Following reconnection, the magnetic field lines penetrate the plane of the current sheet. Prior to reconnection, particle populations on either side of the current sheet were unable to penetrate each other; however, post-reconnection, previously separated plasmas can mix, facilitated by components of the magnetic field normal to the current sheet. In two-dimensional (2D) scenarios, reconnection exclusively takes place at a 2D X-type null point, characterized by magnetic field lines with hyperbolic shapes in close proximity.

Reconnection processes

In 2D configurations, a collisionless magnetic reconnection setup can be subdivided into several components: separatrix, inflow region, outflow region, and ion and electron diffusion regions (refer to Fig. E.2). The separatrix demarcates the inflow and outflow regions, with two separatrices forming an X point. In three-dimensional (3D) reconnection, the X points coalesce to form an X line or separator, while the separatrix transforms into a separatrix surface. Within the ion diffusion region, characterized by a width equivalent to the ion skin depth ($d_i = \frac{c}{\omega_{pi}}$), electrons are unmagnetized, whereas within the electron diffusion region, with a width corresponding to the electron skin depth ($d_e = \frac{c}{\omega_{pe}}$), electrons are also unmagnetized. Here, ω_{pi} , ω_{pe} , and c represent the ion plasma frequency, electron plasma frequency, and the speed of light, respectively (Lee and Lee, 2020).

Early models of magnetic reconnection by Parker (1957), Sweet (1958), Petschek (1964), Sonnerup (1970), and Yeh and Axford (1970) were deemed fundamentally consistent by Vasylunas (1975), each providing unique insights into the process. The reconnection model proposed by Parker (1957) and Sweet (1958) involves the transport of oppositely directed magnetic field lines by the plasma toward the diffusion region, characterized by an inflow speed. The reconnection rate (R) is proportionate to the square root of the plasma resistivity

Figure E.2 **A**. A general schematic diagram sketching different regions in collisionless magnetic reconnection: X point (depicted as a black dot), separatrices (illustrated as green dashed lines), inflow region, outflow region, ion diffusion region (depicted in blue), and electron diffusion region (shown in pink). Solid black lines represent magnetic field lines, and yellow arrows indicate inflow and outflow velocities. Sketches of four classical reconnection models: **B**. Petschek model with slow mode expansion in the inflow region, **C**. Sonnerup and Yeh/Axford model with fast mode expansion in the inflow region, **D** Sweet–Parker current sheet diffusion model where B_1 , U_1 , U_2 , $2l$, and 2δ stand for magnetic field, inflow and outflow velocities, the length, and width of the current layer respectively, and **E**. multiple X line reconnection model (Lee and Fu, 1986). Image reproduced from Lee and Lee (2020).

(η). However, early researchers realized that the classical resistivity resulting from Coulomb collisions, when considered with the global system length, yields a reconnection rate too

small to account for the rapid energy conversion observed in phenomena like solar flares or magnetospheric substorms.

Petschek (1964) proposed an alternative approach, suggesting that energy conversion could also occur through MHD waves or discontinuities. In his model, Petschek confined the diffusion region to a small area, with four slow shocks (SSs) attached to the central diffusion region, as depicted in Fig. E.2B. The conversion of magnetic energy into plasma flow and thermal energies primarily occurs through these SSs. Unlike the Sweet-Parker model, Ohmic heating in the diffusion region is relatively insignificant, and the reconnection rate exhibits weak dependence on resistivity, resulting in a significantly higher reconnection rate.

Sonnerup (1970) and Yeh and Axford (1970) independently developed a model for magnetic reconnection also featuring four SSs, as shown in Fig. E.2C. Vasyliunas (1975) highlighted a major distinction between their model and Petschek's: while Petschek's model involves convergent plasma flow towards the current sheet, the Sonnerup-Yeh-Axford model features divergent flow, or slow mode expansion, towards the current sheet.

Priest and Forbes (1986) introduced a unified family of models for incompressible, steady-state magnetic reconnection. They emphasized the significance of boundary conditions on the inflow boundary in determining the reconnection configuration. By altering these conditions, they could derive models akin to Petschek's and Sonnerup's, as well as new models like hybrid expansion and flux pileup models. While Petschek's model depicts a fast expansion wave in the reconnection inflow region, the Sonnerup-Yeh-Axford model portrays a slow expansion wave. However, observations of both fast and slow expansion waves in the reconnection inflow region have not been reported.

After a period of debate and numerical experimentation, it is now established that fast reconnection (Almost-Uniform or Petschek) may occur under three distinct circumstances: when magnetic diffusivity is enhanced at the X-point due to factors such as micro-turbulence; in collisionless reconnection with the inclusion of the Hall effect; and through turbulent reconnection induced by secondary tearing in current sheets (Refer to Gonzalez and Parker, 2016, and references therein). Ultimately, it's crucial to highlight that in steady-state reconnection, the conversion from magnetic energy to plasma kinetic energy is regulated by the average Alfvén speed, rather than being directly influenced by the specifics of the reconnection process (Gombosi, 1998, Chapter 14).

Appendix F

Cost-Benefit analysis of including HALL-MHD in STORMI calculations

Ledvina et al. (2008) demonstrated that when investigating Earth or an Earth-like (exo)-planetary body with a standard radius of 6400 km and an orbital distance of 1 AU, the stellar wind plasma surrounding the planet exhibits the following normalized plasma parameters: ion gyroradius (r_L/R_E) = 0.10, Debye length (λ_D/R_E) = 1.6×10^{-6} , collisional mean free path (λ_{mfp}/R_E) = 6.4×10^4 , ion skip depth ($c/\omega_{pi}/R_E$) = 0.014, and electron skip depth ($c/\omega_{pe}/R_E$) = 3.1×10^{-4} . They also contended that a resistive MHD model, without incorporating the Hall effect, should suffice in adequately characterizing the plasma environment of Earth provided the scale size is at least larger than $0.1 R_E$. However, given that PLUTO offers a straightforward method to integrate Hall terms, we conducted a cost-benefit analysis to ascertain whether incorporating these terms significantly alters our results. If affirmative, would incorporating Hall terms in the simulation be beneficial, despite incurring additional computational costs?

Primarily, we used a combination of time-stepping schemes in order to incorporate resistivity along with Hall into PLUTO and run the Star Planet Interaction module (CESSI-SPIM) to identify the best possible schemes in this endeavor. We consider equal electron and proton number density and run the module for two hours of physical time such that the magnetosphere can attain a steady state. The details of the computer used for this purpose are given below, whereas the details of each case run, including total RAM usage and run times, are given in Table F.1.

Architecture:	x86_64
CPU op-mode(s):	32-bit, 64-bit
Byte Order:	Little Endian

```

CPU(s): 56
On-line CPU(s) list: 0-55
Thread(s) per core: 1
Core(s) per socket: 28
Socket(s): 2
NUMA node(s): 2
Vendor ID: GenuineIntel
CPU family: 6
Model: 106
Model name: Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6330 CPU @ 2.00GHz
Stepping: 6
CPU MHz: 3100.000
CPU max MHz: 3100.0000
CPU min MHz: 800.0000
BogoMIPS: 4000.00
Virtualization: VT-x
L1d cache: 48K
L1i cache: 32K
L2 cache: 1280K
L3 cache: 43008K
NUMA node0 CPU(s): 0-27
NUMA node1 CPU(s): 28-55
Flags: fpu vme de pse tsc msr pae mce cx8 apic
sep mtrr pge mca cmov pat pse36 clflush
dts acpi mmx fxsr sse sse2 ss ht tm pbe
syscall nx pdpe1gb rdtscp lm constant_tsc
art arch_perfmon pebs bts rep_good nopl
xtopology nonstop_tsc aperfmperf eagerfpu
pni pclmulqdq dtes64 monitor ds_cpl vmx
smx est tm2 ssse3 sdbg fma cx16 xtpr pdcm
pcid dca sse4_1 sse4_2 x2apic movbe popcnt
tsc_deadline_timer aes xsave avx f16c rdrand
lahf_lm abm 3dnowprefetch epb cat_l3
invpcid_single intel_pt ssbd mba ibrs ibpb
stibp ibrs_enhanced tpr_shadow vnmi
flexpriority ept vpid fsgsbase tsc_adjust

```

	Parameters	No resistivity	STS resistivity	Explicit resistivity	RKL resistivity
No Hall	Total allocated memory (Mb)	130.07	190.39	190.39	276.92
	Total run time	4h:31m:4s	7h:1m:58s	8h:11m:40s	10h:5m:5s
	Average time/step (sec)	0.92	1.43	1.66	2.05
Explicit Hall	Total allocated memory (Mb)	146.04	193.24	193.25	279.77
	Total run time	6h:17m:38s	9h:54m:50s	11h:16m:9s	13h:37m:10s
	Average time/step (sec)	1.08	1.70	1.93	2.33

Table F.1 Comparing parameters across various time-stepping methodologies integrating resistivity and Hall effects within MHD simulations conducted with PLUTO. Here STS stands for Super Time Stepping and RKL is Runge-Kutta Legendre; both are time-stepping schemes used in PLUTO.

```

bmi1 hle avx2 smep bmi2 erms invpcid rtm
cqm rdt_a avx512f avx512dq rdseed adx smap
avx512ifma clflushopt clwb avx512cd sha_ni
avx512bw avx512vl xsaveopt xsavec xgetbv1
cqm_llc cqm_occup_llc cqm_mbm_total
cqm_mbm_local dtherm ida arat pln pts
avx512vbmi umip pku ospke avx512_vbmi2
gfni vaes vpclmulqdq avx512_vnni
avx512_bitalg avx512_vpopcntdq md_clear
pconfig spec_ctrl intel_stibp flush_l1d
arch_capabilities

```

Notably, for using any type of scheme, adding Hall terms on top of resistivity causes nearly 20% more time to complete a simulation. We utilized the best possible combo (explicit Hall and STS resistivity) to run the STORMI module for an imaginary ICME with the central axis parallel to the ecliptic normal and negative B_z . The STORMI index and the average current density around the planet show that incorporating the Hall terms changes the results maximally by much less than just 10% (refer to Fig. F.1). This tells us that a resistive MHD model, without incorporating the Hall effect, do suffice in adequately characteriz-

Figure F.1 The figures depict a comparison of STORMI index and volume-averaged J values in STORMI simulations with and without the presence of the Hall term. The shaded green area represents the relative percentage error in these values.

ing the plasma environment of Earth. However, in studies other than prediction, where the computational time doesn't impact much of the motivation, Hall MHD can be used to gain a better physical understanding of the system.

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